

3rd Semester B. Tech (Civil Engineering)
ENGINEERING STATISTICS

Subject Code:	21SMA31	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L)		50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Exam Marks	100
Credits	04	Total Marks	
		Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

The objective of this course is to introduce students to the learn the following:

- Analytical and numerical methods in the different engineering fields by making them to learn Fourier series
- Fourier transforms
- numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations
- Probability
- Joint probability distribution arising in science and engineering

Course Outcomes: On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Know the use of periodic signals and Fourier series to analyze circuits and system communications.
2. Explain the general linear system theory for continuous-time signals and digital signal processing using the Fourier Transform and Employ appropriate numerical methods to solve algebraic and transcendental equations
3. To develop probability distribution of discrete, continuous random variables and joint probability distribution occurring in digital signal processing, design engineering and microwave engineering.
4. The statistical methods of studying data samples, hypothesis testing and statistical quality control, control charts and their properties.
5. Understand how finite volume scheme and finite difference scheme are related.

Module 1

Fourier series: Convergence and divergence of infinite series of positive terms, definition and illustrative examples. Periodic functions, Dirichlet's condition, Fourier Series of periodic functions with period 2π and with arbitrary period $2c$. Half range Fourier Series, practical harmonic analysis-Illustrative examples from engineering field.

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 2

Fourier Transform: Infinite Fourier transforms, Fourier sine and cosine transforms. Inverse Fourier transforms, Problems

Numerical Methods: Numerical solution of algebraic and transcendental equations by Regula- Falsi Method and Newton-Raphson method

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 3

Probability: Introduction. Sample space and events. Axioms of probability. Addition and multiplication theorems. Conditional probability – illustrative examples.

Probability Distributions: Random variables (discrete and continuous), probability mass/density functions. Binomial distribution, Poisson distribution. Exponential and normal distributions, problems
Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 4

Statistical Methods: Review of measures of central tendency and dispersion. Correlation-Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation-problems. Regression analysis- lines of regression (without proof) –problems

Joint probability distribution: Joint Probability distribution for two discrete random variables, expectation, covariance, correlation coefficient

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 5

Numerical solutions of PDE: Classification of PDE s of second order, Numerical solutions of PDE – finite difference approximation to derivatives, Numerical solution of two dimensional Laplace's equation, one dimensional heat and wave equations

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Continuous internal assessment method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each.

01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module.

08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

Text Books:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed.(Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.
3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: "Engineering Mathematics", Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

Reference Books:

1. C.Ray Wylie, Louis C.Barrett :“Advanced Engineering Mathematics”, 6th Edition, 2. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S.S.Sastry: “Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis”, 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B.V.Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal, “A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics”, Laxmi Publications. Latest edition, 2014.
5. Chandrika Prasad and Reena Garg “Advanced Engineerig mathematics, Latest edition, Khanna Publishing, 2018.

3rd Semester B. Tech
STRENGTH OF MATERIALS

Sub Code : 21SCV32
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To learn fundamental concepts of stress, strain and deformation of solids with applications to bars, beams and thin shells.
2. To know the mechanism of load transfer in beams, the induced stress resultants and deformations.
3. To understand the effect of torsion on shafts and springs.
4. To analyze two dimensional state of stress and plane trusses.
5. To give an ability to apply the knowledge of strength of materials on engineering applications and design problems.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to apply the linear laws of elasticity as related to stresses and strains.
- CO2:** Able to understand the behavior of columns and struts under axial loading and also the effect of combined axial and bending stress.
- CO3:** Able to provide students with exposure to the systematic methods for solving engineering problems in solid mechanics.
- CO4:** Able to analyze and design structural members subjected to tension, compression, torsion, bending and combined stresses using the fundamental concepts of stress, strain and elastic behavior of materials.
- CO5:** Able to build the necessary theoretical background for further structural analysis.

MODULE 1

SIMPLE STRESS AND STRAIN

Introduction, Definition and concept and of stress and strain. Hooke's law, Stress-Strain diagrams for ferrous and non-ferrous materials, factor of safety, Elongation of tapering bars of circular and rectangular cross sections, Elongation due to self-weight. Saint Venant's principle, Compound bars, Temperature stresses, Compound section subjected to temperature stresses, state of simple shear, Elastic constants and their relationship. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

COMPOUND STRESSES

Introduction, state of stress at a point, General two dimensional stress system, Principal stresses and principal planes. Mohr's circle of stresses.

THIN AND THICK CYLINDERS:

Introduction, Thin cylinders subjected to internal pressure; Hoop stresses, Longitudinal stress and change in volume. Thick cylinders subjected to both internal and external pressure; Lamé's equation, radial and hoop stress distribution. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

SHEAR FORCE AND BENDING MOMENT IN BEAMS

Introduction to types of beams, supports and loadings. Definition of bending moment and shear force, Sign conventions, relationship between load intensity, bending moment and shear force. Shear force and bending moment diagrams for statically determinate beams subjected to points load, uniformly distributed loads, uniformly varying loads, couple and their combinations. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

BENDING AND SHEAR STRESSES IN BEAMS

Introduction, pure bending theory, Assumptions, derivation of bending equation, modulus of rupture, section modulus, flexural rigidity. Expression for transverse shear stress in beams, Bending and shear stress distribution diagrams for circular, rectangular, 'I', and 'T' sections. Shear center(only concept)

COLUMNS AND STRUTS:

Introduction, short and long columns. Euler's theory; Assumptions, Derivation for Euler's Buckling load for different end conditions, Limitations of Euler's theory. Rankine - Gordon's formula for columns.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

TORSION IN CIRCULAR SHAFT

Torsion in Circular Shaft: Introduction, pure torsion, Assumptions, derivation of torsion equation for circular shafts, torsional rigidity and polar modulus Power transmitted by a shaft, combined bending and torsion.

Theories of Failure: Introduction, maximum principal stress theory (Rankine's theory), Maximum shearing stress theory (Tresca's theory), Strain energy theory (Beltrami and Haigh), and maximum strain theory (St. Venant's theory). **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Strength of Materials, Subramanyam, Oxford University Press, Edition2008
2. Mechanics of Materials, B.C Punmia Ashok Jain, Arun Jain, Lakshmi Publications, New Delhi.
3. Strength of Materials, Basavarajaiah and Mahadevappa Universities Press (2009).

REFERENCES

1. Strength of Materials, Singer Harper and Row Publications.
2. Elements of Strength of Materials, Timoshenko and Young Affiliated East-West Press.
3. Mechanics of Materials, James M. Gere (5th Edition), Thomson Learning.

3rd Semester B. Tech
FLUID MECHANICS

Sub Code : 21SCV33
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To impart thorough understanding of the properties of the fluids, behavior of fluids under static conditions.
2. To develop understanding about hydrostatic law, principle of buoyancy and stability of a floating body and application of mass, momentum and energy equation in fluid flow
3. The dynamics of fluids is introduced through the control volume approach which gives an integrated understanding of the transport of mass, momentum and energy.
4. To expose to the applications of the conservation laws to a) flow measurements b) flow through pipes (both laminar and turbulent)
5. To determine the losses in a flow system, flow through pipes, boundary layer flow and flow past immersed bodies.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To describe appropriate physical properties and show how these allow differentiation between solids and fluids as well as between liquids and gases.
- CO2:** Able to determine pressures and forces on submerged bodies.
- CO3:** Able to analyze flow rates, velocities, energy losses and momentum flux for fluid system and also understand the fundamentals of laminar and turbulent boundary layer.
- CO4:** To present data or governing equations in non-dimensional form, design experiments, and perform model studies.
- CO5:** Able to decide when appropriate to use ideal flow concepts and the Bernoulli equation.

MODULE 1

FLUIDS & THEIR PROPERTIES: Concept of fluid, Systems of units. Properties of fluid; Mass density, Specific weight, Specific gravity, Specific volume, Viscosity, Cohesion, Adhesion, Surface tension & Capillarity. Fluid as a continuum, Newton's law of viscosity (theory & problems). Capillary rise in a vertical tube and between two plane surfaces (theory & problems). Vapor pressure of liquid, compressibility and bulk modulus, capillarity, surface tension, pressure inside a water droplet, pressure inside a soap bubble and liquid jet. Numerical problems

FLUID PRESSURE AND ITS MEASUREMENTS: Definition of pressure, Pressure at a point, Pascal's law, Variation of pressure with depth. Types of pressure. Measurement of pressure using simple, differential & inclined manometers (theory & problems). Introduction to Mechanical and electronic pressure measuring devices.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

HYDROSTATIC FORCES ON SURFACES: Definition, Total pressure, center of pressure, total pressure on horizontal, vertical and inclined plane surface, total pressure on curved surfaces, water pressure on gravity dams, Lock gates. Numerical Problems.

FUNDAMENTALS OF FLUID FLOW (KINEMATICS): Introduction. Methods of describing fluid motion. Velocity and Total acceleration of a fluid particle. Types of fluid flow, Description of flow pattern. Basic principles of fluid flow, three-dimensional continuity equation in Cartesian coordinate system. Derivation for Rotational and irrotational motion. Potential function, stream function, orthogonality of streamlines and equipotential lines. Numerical problems on Stream function and velocity potential. Introduction to flow net. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

FLUID DYNAMICS

Introduction. Forces acting on fluid in motion. Euler's equation of motion along a streamline and Bernoulli's equation. Assumptions and limitations of Bernoulli's equation. Modified Bernoulli's equation. Problems on applications of Bernoulli's equation (with and without losses). Vortex motion; forced vortex, free vortex, problems. Momentum equation problems on pipe bends.

Applications: Introduction. Venturi meter, Orifice meter, Pitot tube. Numerical Problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

ORIFICE AND MOUTHPIECE: Introduction, classification, flow through orifice, hydraulic coefficients, and Numerical problems. Mouthpiece, classification, Borda's Mouthpiece.

NOTCHES AND WEIRS: Introduction. Classification, discharge over rectangular, triangular, trapezoidal notches, Cipolletti notch, broad crested weirs. Numerical problems. Ventilation of weirs, submerged weirs. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

FLOW THROUGH PIPES: Introduction. Major and minor losses in pipe flow. Darcy-Weisbach equation for head loss due to friction in a pipe. Pipes in series, pipes in parallel, equivalent pipe-problems. Minor losses in pipe flow, equation for head loss due to sudden expansion. Numerical problems. Hydraulic gradient line, energy gradient line. Pipe Networks, Water hammers in pipes, Problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. 'A Text Book of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Rajput, S. Chand & Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. 'Principles of Fluid Mechanics and Fluid Machines'- N. Narayana Pillai, Universities Press (India), Hyderabad, 2009 Edition.
3. 'Fluid Mechanics and Turbo machines'- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCES

1. 'Fundamentals of Fluid Mechanics' – Bruce R. Munson, Donald F. Young, Theodore H. Okiishi, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. 'Introduction To Fluid Mechanics' – Edward J. Shaughnessy, Jr; Ira m. Katz; James p Schaffer, Oxford. University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition.
3. 'Text Book of Fluid Mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
5. 'Fluid Mechanics' – Streeter, Wylie, Bedford New Delhi, 2008 Edition.

3RD Semester B. Tech ENGINEERING SURVEYING

Sub Code : 21SCV34
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to understand the different methods and techniques of surveying like levelling, compass survey, contouring and curve settings etc. and their applications in surveying.
- CO2:** Able to use survey instruments in carrying out survey, to collect data, and write reports and able to perform required calculations to achieve the objective for different types of surveying for different Engineering projects.
- CO3:** Able to apply the concept of Tacheometry for surveying in difficult and hilly areas to obtain the topographical map of area.
- CO4:** Able to control the accumulation of errors in projects.
- CO5:** Able to use modern survey equipment to measure angle and distances.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION TO CIVIL ENGINEERING SURVEYING: Introduction: Definition of surveying, Objectives and importance of surveying. Classification of surveys. Principles of surveying. Units of measurements, Surveying measurements and errors, types of errors, precision and accuracy. Classification of maps, map scale, conventional symbols, topographic maps, map layout, Survey of India Map numbering systems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

MEASUREMENT OF HORIZONTAL DISTANCES: Measuring tape and types. Measurement using tapes, taping on level ground and sloping ground. Errors and corrections in tape measurements, ranging of lines, direct and indirect methods of ranging, Electronic distance measurement, basic principle. Booking of tape survey work, Field book, entries

COMPASS SURVEY: Basic definitions; meridians, bearings, magnetic and true bearings. Prismatic and surveyor's compasses, temporary adjustments, declination. Quadrantal bearings, whole circle bearings, local attraction and related problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

LEVELING: Basic terms and definitions, Methods of leveling, Dumpy level, auto level, digital and

laser levels. Curvature and refraction corrections. Booking and reduction of levels. Differential leveling, profile leveling, fly leveling, check leveling, reciprocal leveling, trigonometric leveling (heights and distances-single plane and double plane methods).

THEODOLITE: Theodolite and types, Fundamental axes and parts of Transit Theodolite, uses of Theodolite, Temporary adjustments of transit Theodolite, measurement of horizontal and vertical angles- Method of repetitions and reiterations, step by step procedure for obtaining permanent adjustment of Transit Theodolite. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

PLANE TABLE SURVEYING

Plane table and accessories, Advantages and limitations of plane table survey, Orientation and methods of orientation, Methods of plotting – Radiation, Intersection, Traversing, Resection method, Two point and three point problems, Solution to two point problem by graphical method, Solution to three point problem Bessel’s graphical method, Errors in plane table survey. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

AREAS AND VOLUMES: Measurement of area by dividing the area into geometrical figures, area from offsets, mid ordinate rule, trapezoidal and Simpson’s one third rule, area from co-ordinates, introduction to planimeter, digital planimeter. Measurement of volumes- trapezoidal and prismoidal formula.

CONTOURING: Contours, Methods of contouring, Interpolation of contours, contour gradient, characteristics of contours and uses. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

TEXT BOOKS

1. 'Surveying' Vol.-1, B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. 'Plane Surveying' Vol-1-A.M. Chandra, Newage International @Ltd.
3. 'Plane Surveying' – ALAK, S. Chand and Company Ltd., NewDelhi.

REFERENCES

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
2. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
3. Surveying Vol. I, S.K. Duggal

3RD Semester B. Tech

BUILDING MATERIALS AND SMART MATERIALS

Sub Code :	21SCV35	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3T	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
Mode of delivery:	PBL	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To develop in recognizing the good materials to be used for the construction work
2. To develop investigation of soil condition, deciding and design of suitable foundation for different structures
3. To develop supervision of different types of masonry
4. To impart in selection of materials, design and supervision of suitable type of floor and roof.
5. To develop and utilize the smart materials in the building structures

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand the properties of natural and advance building materials
- CO2:** Able to design and test the materials either in the laboratory or in the field before their actual use at the site.
- CO3:** To attain the knowledge of different components of building, their classification, materials and methods of construction and causes of their failures.
- CO4:** To impart the knowledge about the characteristics, sources and defects in various materials used for construction purposes.
- CO5:** Able to decide appropriate smart technologies to be used in the structures.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION TO BUILDING MATERIALS: Stone as building material; Requirement of good building stones, dressing of stones, Deterioration and Preservation of stone work. Compressive strength, water absorption, efflorescence, dimension and warpage. Mortar - types and requirements. Timber as construction material, Fine aggregate - Natural and manufactured – Sieve analysis, zoning, specify gravity, bulking, moisture content, deleterious materials. Coarse aggregate: Natural and manufactured - importance of size, shape and texture. Grading of aggregates, Sieve analysis, specific gravity, Flakiness and elongation index, crushing, impact and abrasion tests. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

BRICKS: Classification, Manufacturing of clay bricks, Requirement of good bricks. Field and laboratory tests on bricks; Cement Concrete blocks, Stabilized Mud Blocks, Sizes, requirement of good blocks.

DEFINITION AND TERMS USED IN MASONRY: Brick masonry, characteristics and requirements of good brick masonry, Bonds in brick work, Header, Stretcher, English, Flemish bond, Stone masonry, Requirements of good stonemasonry, Classification, characteristics of different stone masonry, Joints in stone masonry. Types of walls; load bearing, partition walls, cavity walls.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

LINTELS AND ARCHES: Definition, function and classification of lintels, Balconies, chejja and canopy. Arches; Elements and Stability of an Arch.

FLOORS: Requirement of good floor, Components of ground floor, Selection of flooring material, Laying of Concrete, Marble, Granite, Tile flooring, Cladding of tiles

DOORS, WINDOWS AND VENTILATORS: Location of doors and windows, technical terms, Materials for doors and windows, Paneled door, Flush door, Collapsible door, Rolling shutter, PVC Door, Paneled and glazed Window, Bay Window, French window. Ventilators. Sizes as per IS recommendations. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

FORMWORK: Introduction to form work, scaffolding, shoring, under pinning.

PLASTERING AND POINTING: Plastering and Pointing: Purpose, materials and methods of plastering and pointing, defects in plastering - Stucco plastering, lathe plastering, Damp proofing-causes, effects and methods.

PAINTS: Purpose, types, ingredients and defects, Preparation and applications of paints to new and old plastered surfaces. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

INTRODUCTION TO SMART BUILDINGS: Introduction to Intelligent buildings - Basic concepts – Intelligent building automation - Building automation system - Cost analysis of intelligent buildings – Introduction to smart materials.

INTRODUCTION TO SMART MATERIALS AND STRUCTURES: Instrumented Structures Functions And Response– Sensing systems – Self diagnosis – Signal processing consideration – Actuation systems and effectors.

BUILDING SYSTEMS: Lighting – day lighting; ventilation – natural ventilation; indoor air quality; heating/cooling – geothermal; passive and active systems for energy production and conservation; water conservation – grey water reuse, water saving plumbing fixtures. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Brain Culshaw – Smart Structure and Materials Artech House – Borton, London-1996.
2. Srinivasan ,A.V and Michael McFarland . D, “Smart Structures – Analysis and Design, Cambridge University Press, 2001.
3. Engineering Materials, Rangawala P.C. Charter Publishing House, Anand, India.
4. Engineering Materials, Sushil Kumar, Standard Publication and Distributors, New Delhi.
5. Concrete technology – Theory and practice, M.S. Shetty, S. Chand and Co, New Delhi, 2002.

REFERENCES

1. A Text Book Building Materials, by P.G. Varghese, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., Publication.
2. Advances in Building Materials and Construction by Mohan Rai and M.P. Jain Singh – publication by CBRI, Roorkee.
3. Concrete Technology, Neville A.M and Brooks J.J — ELBS Edition. London.
4. Concrete Technology – Gambhir M.L –Dhanpat Rai and Sons, New Delhi.

3rd Semester B. Tech
COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL36
Hrs/ Week : 1T+2L
Credits : 2
Mode of delivery: BM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To learn the programming of numerical methods
2. To use the computer to apply numerical techniques
3. To learn the fundamentals of Computer Aided Drafting
4. To understand Civil Engineering Drawing concepts
5. To learn the handling of spreadsheets

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to develop programs for numerical methods
CO2: Able to solve numerical techniques in computer
CO3: Able to implement Computer Aided Drafting
CO4: Able to apply Building concepts to Civil Engineering
CO5: Able to apply Spreadsheet calculations to Civil Engineering

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. AUTOCAD

1.1 Basics of AUTOCAD:

DRAWING TOOLS: Lines, Circle, Arc, Polyline, Multiline, Polygon, Rectangle, Spline, Ellipse,
Modify tools: Erase, Copy, Mirror, Offset, Array, Move, Rotate, Scale, Stretch, Lengthen, Trim, Extend, Break, Chamfer and Fillet, *Using Text:* Single line text, Multiline text, Spelling, Edit text, Special Features: View tools, Layers concept, Dimension tools, Hatching, Customising toolbars, working with multiple drawings

1.2 USE OF AUTOCAD IN CIVIL ENGINEERING DRAWINGS:

Following drawings are to be prepared for the data given using AUTOCAD

- i) Cross section of Foundation - masonry wall, RCC columns (isolated)
- ii) Different types of staircases
- iii) Lintel and chajja
- iv) RCC slabs and beams
- v) Drawing of Plan, elevation and sectional elevation of single storied residential and public buildings given the single line diagram and preparing excavation plan.

2. STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS SOFTWARE

Use of commercially available software for the analysis of

- i) Plane Trusses
- ii) Continuous beams
- iii) 2D Portal frames-single storied and multistoried

3. USE OF EXCEL IN CIVIL ENGINEERING PROBLEMS

Use of spread sheet for the following civil engineering problems

- i) SFD and BMD for Cantilever and simply supported beam subjected to uniformly distributed and uniformly varying load acting throughout the span
- ii) Design of singly reinforced and doubly reinforced rectangular beams
- iii) Computation of earthwork
- iv) Design of horizontal curve by offset method
- v) Design of super elevation

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Computer Aided Design Laborator - Dr M.N. Shesha Prakash, Dr.G.S.Suresh, Lakshmi Publications
2. CAD Laboratory- M.A.Jayaram, D.S.Rajendra Prasad- Sapna Publications
3. AUTOCAD 2002- Roberts JT, BPB publications.

REFERENCES

1. AUTOCAD 2004- Sham Tickoo, A beginner's Guide, WileyDreamech India Pvt Ltd.
2. Learning Excel 2002- Ramesh Bangia, Khanna Book PublishingCo (P) Ltd.
3. Microsoft Excel- Mathieson SA, Starfire Publishers.

3rd Semester B. Tech
SMART MATERIAL TESTING LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL37
Hrs/ Week : 2L
Credits : 1
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 25
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 25
Total Hours : 30

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To understand the characteristics of materials used in construction.
2. To understand the behavior of civil engineering materials used in buildings under different loading conditions.
3. To understand the importance of grading of aggregates
4. To operate and practical exposure of UTM to conduct test on various building materials
5. To demonstrate strain gauges and strain indicators

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to study the stress-strain curves of different materials used in the field under different loading conditions.
- CO2:** Able to differentiate between properties of materials affect strength under various conditions.
- CO3:** Able to calculate simple tensile and shear stress using the appropriate guidelines and formats.
- CO4:** Able to analyze the bending stress on different types of sections.
- CO5:** Able to understand deflection of different sections at different loading conditions.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. Tension test on Mild steel and HYSD bars.
2. Compression test of Mild Steel, Cast iron and Wood.
3. Torsion test on Mild Steel circular sections
4. Bending Test on Wood Under two point loading
5. Shear Test on Mild steel.
6. Impact test on Mild Steel (Charpy & Izod)
7. Hardness tests on ferrous and non-ferrous metals – Brinell's, Rockwelland Vicker's
8. Test on Bricks and Tiles
9. Tests on Fine aggregates – Moisture content, Specific gravity, Bulkdensity, Sieve analysis and Bulking
10. Tests on Coarse aggregates – Absorption, Moisture content, specificgravity, Bulk density and Sieve analysis
11. Demonstration of Strain gauges and Strain indicators

NOTE: All tests to be carried out as per relevant BIS Codes.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 10 marks
ONE question from minor experiments: 210 marks
Viva – voce = 05 marks
Total: 25 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Testing of Engineering Materials, Davis, Troxell and Hawk, International Student Edition – McGraw Hill Book Co. New Delhi.
2. Mechanical Testing of Materials”, Fenner, George Newnes Ltd. London.
3. “Experimental Strength of Materials”, Holes K A, English Universities Press Ltd. London.
4. “Testing of Metallic Materials”, Surya Narayana A K, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Relevant IS Codes
2. “Material Testing Laboratory Manual”, Kukreja C B- Kishore K. Ravi Chawla Standard Publishers & Distributors 1996.
3. Concrete Manual, M.L. Gambhir –Dhanpat Rai & Sons- New Delhi.

EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME - 1

Subject Code	21SQA38	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations with Domain specific training in respective branches.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Learn domain specific knowledge
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART – A

Number System –

- a. Number system
- b. Power cycle
- c. Remainder cycle
- d. Factors, Multiples
- e. HCF and LCM
- f. Trailing Zeroes,

Data arrangements and Blood relations –

- a. Linear Arrangement
- b. Circular Arrangement
- c. Multi-dimensional Arrangement
- d. Blood Relation
- e. Option elimination method in Blood Relation

Time and work –

- a. Work with different efficiencies
- b. Alternate day work
- c. Pipes and cisterns

- d. Work equivalence
- e. Division of wages
- f. Leaving the work concept with example

Coding & decoding, Number Series, Analogy, Odd man out –

- a. Different types of Problems on Coding and Decoding
- b. Mixed Series, alternate Series, mixed operational series
- c. Analogy
- d. Odd Man Out

Reading comprehension –

- a. Types and Tackling Strategies.
- b. Understanding meaning of a text.
- c. Drawing Connections.
- d. Summarizing and Synthesizing.
- e. Building Vocabulary.
- f. Speed Reading Strategies.

Antonyms & Synonyms –

- a. Understanding root words.
- b. Prefixes.
- c. Suffixes.
- d. Vocabulary building.
- e. Putting words into context.
- f. Word Power made easy.
- g. Elimination.

PART – B

Strength of Materials

Engineering Mechanics

Building Materials

Fluid Mechanics

Survey

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books:

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

3rd Semester B.Tech
CIVIL ENGINEERING SURVEYING LABORATORY

Sub Code :	21SCVL39	IA Marks :	25
Hrs/ Week :	2L	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	1	Exam Marks:	25
Mode of delivery :	RM	Total Hours:	30

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Apply the basic principles of engineering surveying and measurements
- Follow effectively field procedures required for a professional surveyor
- Use techniques, skills and conventional surveying instruments necessary for engineering Practice.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to apply the concept of accuracy of the line diagram.
- CO2:** Students will be able to know the concept of elevation between two points using fly leveling technique
- CO3:** Students will be able to understand the measurement of vertical angles using Theodolite.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand Curve setting by different methods.
- CO5:** Students will able to understand the surveying by using total station.

Experiments

1. To check the accuracy of the line diagram of the building plan by 3,4,5 method.
2. To determine difference in elevation between two points using fly leveling technique & to conduct fly back leveling. Booking of levels using both HI and Rise & Fall methods using Dumpy Level.
3. Study of Theodolite -measurement of vertical angles, Measurement of horizontal angles by method of repetition.
4. Measurement of horizontal angles by method of reiteration.
5. Trigonometric Leveling - Heights and distance problem (Two Exercises)
6. Heights and distance using Principles of tachometric surveying (Two Exercises)
7. Curve setting – different methods. (Two Exercises)
8. Determine of area using total station.
9. Traversing using total station
10. Contouring using total station
11. Determination of remote height using total station
12. Stake out using total station.
13. Distance, gradient, diff, height between two inaccessible points using total station.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major
experiments: 20 marks ONE
question from minor experiments:
20 marks Viva – voce = 10 marks
Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol.–1, B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. "Plane Surveying' Vol-1-A.M. Chandra, Newage International ® Ltd.
3. 'Plane Surveying' – ALAK, S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS :

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
2. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
3. Surveying Vol. I, S.K. Duggal

INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	21SQA30	IA Marks	-
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method

- Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MANGALURU

ADDITIONAL MATHEMATICS - I

(Mandatory Learning Course: Common to All Branches)

(A Bridge course for Lateral Entry students of III Sem. B. Tech.)

Course Title: Additional Mathematics - I

Contact Hours/Week : 02

Total Hours: 25

Exam. Marks : 50

Course Code : 21SMADIP301

L-T-P : 2-0-0

Exam. Hours : 02

Credits : 00

Course Objectives:

The mandatory learning course **21SMADIP301** viz., **Additional Mathematics-I** aims to provide

1. basic concepts of complex trigonometry
2. vector algebra
3. differential
4. integral calculus
5. vector differentiation

Course Outcomes:

On completion of the course, students are able to:

1. Understand the fundamental concepts of complex numbers and vector algebra to analyze the problems arising in related area.
2. Use derivatives and partial derivatives to calculate rates of change of multivariate functions.
3. Learn techniques of integration including double and triple integrals to find area, volume mass and moment of inertia of plane and solid region.
4. Analyze position, velocity and acceleration in two or three dimensions using the calculus of vector valued functions.
5. Recognize and solve first-order ordinary differential equations occurring in different branches of engineering.

MODULE 1

Complex Trigonometry: Complex Numbers: Definitions & properties. Modulus and amplitude of a complex number, Argand's diagram, De-Moivre's theorem (without proof)

Vector Algebra: Scalar and vectors. Vectors addition and subtraction. Multiplication of vectors (Dot and Cross products). Scalar and vector triple products simple problems. **05 hours**

MODULE 2

Differential Calculus: Review of successive differentiation. Formulae for nth derivatives of standard functions- Polar curves –angle between the radius vector and the tangent - Problems. Maclaurin's series expansions- Illustrative examples. **05 hours**

MODULE 3

Partial Differentiation : Euler's theorem for homogeneous functions of two variables. Total derivatives differentiation of composite function. Application to Jacobians. **05 hours**

MODULE 4

Integral Calculus: Statement of reduction formulae for $\sin^n x$, $\cos^n x$ and $\sin^n x \cos^n x$ and evaluation of these with standard limits-Examples. Double integrals-Simple examples. **05 hours**

MODULE 5

Vector Differentiation: Differentiation of vector functions. Velocity and acceleration of a particle moving on a space curve. Scalar and vector point functions. Gradient, Divergence, Curl and Laplacian (Definitions only). Solenoidal and irrotational vector fields problems. **05 hours**

Question paper pattern:

- **PART A: TEN** multiple choice questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

[01 mark*10 Questions = 10 marks]

- **PART B: TWO** question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

[08 mark*5 Questions = 40 marks]

Text Book:

1. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna publishers, 43rd edition 2018

Reference books:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed., 2015.
2. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal: Engineering Mathematics, Laxmi Publishers, 7th Ed., 2007

4th Semester B. Tech
NUMERICAL TECHNIQUES AND INTEGRAL TRANSFORMS

Subject Code	21SMA41	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture	4 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Hours/Week			
Total Number of	50	Total Marks	100
Lecture Hours			
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

The purpose of this course is to make students well conversant with the following

1. Numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations
2. complex analysis techniques applied to diverse situation in engineering
3. sampling theory will reflect the range of variation in the population
4. stochastic processes arising in science and engineering
5. numerical methods for ordinary differential equations

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Understand the analyticity, potential fields, residues and poles of complex potentials in field theory and electromagnetic theory.
- CO2: To solve the problems using linear multistep methods
- CO3: Initial-value problems, Runge-Kutta methods, large systems and method of lines; error estimation and control; continuous output; event location.
- CO4: One-step and multi-step methods for non-stiff systems of ordinary differential Equations.
- CO5: Draw the validity of the hypothesis proposed for the given sampling distribution in accepting or rejecting the hypothesis.

Module 1

Analytic function: Review of a function of a complex variable, limits, continuity and differentiability. Analytic functions-Cauchy-Riemann equations in Cartesian and polar forms (no proof). Properties and construction of analytic functions by Milne Thomson method. Singularities, Poles, Residues, Cauchy's residue theorem (statement only).

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 2

Laplace transforms: Laplace transforms of elementary functions. Transforms of derivatives and integrals, transforms of periodic function and unit step function-Problems only.

Inverse Laplace transform: convolution theorem to find the inverse Laplace transform (without proof). Solutions of linear differential equation using Laplace transform.

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 3

Numerical solution of ordinary differential equations: Numerical solution of simultaneous first order ordinary differential equation and first degree, Taylor's series method, Modified Euler's method, Runge kutta method of fourth order. Milne's and Adam's bashforth predictor and creditor method.

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 4

Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations:

Numerical solution of simultaneous differential equation, Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations, Runge-Kutta method and Milne's method. (No derivations of formulae).

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Module 5

Sampling Theory: Sampling, Sampling distributions, standard error, test of hypothesis for means and proportions, confidence limits for means, student's t-distribution, Chi-square distribution as a test of goodness of fit.

Teaching Pedagogy: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. 10 Hours

Continuous internal assessment method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

$$1 \text{ Marks} \times 10 = \mathbf{10 \text{ Marks}}$$

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks.**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed. (Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.

3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: “Engineering Mathematics”, Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C.Ray Wylie, Louis C.Barrett :“Advanced Engineering Mathematics”, 6th Edition, 2. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S.S.Sastry: “Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis”, 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B.V.Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal, “A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics”, 2016.

4th Semester B. Tech
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS -I

Sub Code : 21SCV42
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To impart the principles of elastic structural analysis and behavior of determinate structures.
2. To impart knowledge about various methods involved in the analysis of determinate structures.
3. To apply these methods for analyzing the indeterminate structures to evaluate the response of structures
4. To enable the student get a feeling of how real-life structures behave
5. To make the student familiar with latest computational techniques and software used for structural analysis.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to interpret the various methods of structural displacements.
CO2: Able to analyze the determinate structure and its reaction diagram.
CO3: Able to draw the influence line diagram for rolling loads.
CO4: Able to compute the pressure on supporting tower, suspension bridge etc. and to calculate loads for no tension criteria on domes chimneys and retaining walls.
CO5: Able to interpret the various methods of structural displacements.

MODULE 1

STRUCTURAL SYSTEMS AND ENERGY CONCEPT

Forms of structures, Conditions of equilibrium, Degree of freedom, Linear and Nonlinear structures, one, two, three dimensional structural systems, Determinate and indeterminate structures (Static and Kinematics). Strain energy and complimentary strain energy, Strain energy due to axial load, bending and shear, Theorem of minimum potential energy, Law of conservation of energy and Principle of virtual work. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

DEFLECTION OF BEAMS Moment area method, Conjugate beam method.

The first and second theorem of Castigliano, problems on beams, frames and trusses, Betti's law, Clarke - Maxwell's theorem of reciprocal deflection. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

ANALYSIS OF BEAMS AND PLANE TRUSSES BY STRAIN ENERGY Analysis of beams (Propped cantilever and fixed beams) and trusses using strain energy and unit load methods.

ARCHES AND CABLES

Three hinged circular and parabolic arches with supports at same levels and different levels, Determination of thrust, shear and bending moment. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

ARCHES AND CABLES

Analysis of cables under point loads and UDL, length of cables (Supports at same levels and at different levels).

ANALYSIS OF BEAMS

Consistent deformation method – Propped cantilever and fixed beams. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

Clapeyron's theorem of three moments – continuous beams and fixed beams.

ANALYSIS OF ARCHES

Two hinged parabolic arch, two hinged Circular Arch.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Theory of Structures, Pandit and Guptha, Vol. – I, Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.
2. Basic Structural Analysis Reddy C. S., Tata Mc Graw Hill, New Delhi.
3. Strength of Materials and theory of structures Vol I & II, B.C. Purnia, R.K., Jain Laxmi Publication New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Elementary Structural Analysis, Norris and Wilbur, International Student Edition. McGraw Hill Book Co: New York.
2. Structural Analysis, 4th SI Edition by Amit Prasanth & Aslam Kassimali, Thomson Learning.
3. Analysis of Structures, Thandava Murthy, Oxford University Press.

4th Semester B. Tech
HYDRAULICS AND HYDRAULIC MACHINES

Sub Code :	21SCV43	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3T	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
Mode of delivery:	RM	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To make the student /learn about the model and prototype relationship and able to predict the prototype behavior by model testing in the laboratory.
2. To impart knowledge about the working and design aspects of hydraulic machines like turbines and pumps and their applications.
3. To make the student confident in the fundamental concepts of open channel hydraulics.
4. To impart the knowledge of impact of jet of water on vanes
5. Imparts the knowledge of heads and efficiencies of pumps and turbines

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Student will be able to develop empirical relationships amongst physical variables involved in physical flow phenomenon.

- CO2:** Student will be able to design various components of pumps and turbines and study characteristics
- CO3:** Student will be able to develop velocity triangles on different vanes.
- CO4:** Able to classify the flow in open channel and various momentum principles in open channels.
- CO5:** Able to compute water surface profile by different approaches and to analyze hydraulic jump energy dissipation.

MODULE 1

DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS AND MODEL STUDIES

Introduction, Systems of units, Dimensions of quantities, Dimensional Homogeneity of an equation. Analysis - Rayleigh's method, Buckingham's Π theorem - problems. Model Studies, Similitude, Non-dimensional numbers: Froude models-Undistorted and Distorted models. Reynolds's models - Problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS

Introduction, Geometric properties of Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels. Chezy's equation, Manning's equation-problems. Most economical open channels - Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels - problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

NON-UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS: Introduction, Specific energy, Specific energy diagram, Critical depth, Conditions for Critical flow - Theory & problems. Hydraulic jump in a Horizontal Rectangular Channel – Theory and problems. Dynamic equation for Non-Uniform flow in an Open channel. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

IMPACT OF JET ON FLAT VANES: Introduction, Impulse- Momentum equation. Direct impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, Oblique impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, direct impact on a moving plate, direct impact of a jet on a series of flat vanes on a wheel. Conditions for maximum hydraulic efficiency. Impact of a jet on hinged flat plate- problems.

IMPACT OF JET ON CURVED VANES

Introduction, Force exerted by a jet on a fixed curved vane, moving curved vane. Introduction to concept of velocity triangles, Impact of jet on a series of curved vanes-problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

PELTON WHEEL: Introduction to Turbines, Classification of Turbines. Pelton wheel - components, working and velocity triangles. Maximum power, efficiency, working proportions- problems.

KAPLAN TURBINES: Introduction, Components, Working and Velocity triangles, Properties of the Turbine, Discharge of the Turbines, Number of Blades-Problems. Draft Tube: Types, efficiency of a Draft tube. Introduction to Cavitation in Turbines.

CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS: Introduction, Classification, Priming, Heads and Efficiencies. Equation for work done, minimum starting speed, velocity triangles. Multistage Centrifugal Pumps (Pumps in Series and Pumps in parallel), Problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. 'A Text Book of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Rajput, S. Chand & Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. 'Text Book of Fluid Mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
3. 'Fluid Mechanics and Turbo machines'- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCES

1. 'Introduction to Fluid Mechanics' – Robert W. Fox: Philip J. Pritchard: Alan t. McDonald, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. 'Introduction To Fluid Mechanics' – Edward J. Shaughnessy Jr; Ira m. Katz;; James p Schaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition.
3. 'Hydraulics and Fluid Mechanics' – Dr. P.N. Modi & Dr S.M. Seth, Standard Book House- New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

4th Semester B. Tech

ADVANCED SURVEYING AND ARIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY

Sub Code :	21SCV44	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3T	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	4	Exam Marks:	50
Mode of delivery:	RM	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to Prepare the survey sheet according to the method used.

CO2: Able to record the reduced levels using various methods of leveling and measurement of horizontal; vertical angles by Theodolite.

CO3: Able to apply theoretical considerations in field and other engineering projects.

CO4: Able to determine the location of any point horizontally and vertically using Tachometry.

CO5: Able to understand the concept of aerial photogrammetry.

MODULE 1

CURVE SURVEYING: Curves – Necessity – Types, Simple curves, Elements , Designation of curves, Setting out simple curves by linear methods (numerical problems on offsets from long chord & chord produced method), Setting out curves by Rankines deflection angle method (numerical problems). Compound curves, Elements, Design of compound curves, Setting out of compound curves (numerical problems). Reverse curve between two parallel straights (numerical problems on Equal

radius and unequal radius). Transition curves Characteristics, numerical problems on Length of Transition curve, Vertical curves –Types – (theory). **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

CURVE SETTING (SIMPLE CURVES): Curves – Necessity – Types, Simple curves, Elements, Designation of curves, setting out simple curves by linear methods, setting out curves by Rankine’s deflection angle method.

COMPOUND AND REVERSE CURVES: Compound curves; Elements; Design of compound curves; Setting out of compound curves Reverse curve between two parallel straights (Equal radius and unequal radius).

TRANSITION AND VERTICAL CURVES: Transition curves; Characteristics; Length of Transition curve; Setting out cubic Parabola and Bernoulli’s Lemniscates, Vertical curves –Types – Simple numerical problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

INTRODUCTION TO FIELD ASTRONOMY:

Earth, celestial sphere, earth and celestial coordinate systems, spherical triangle, astronomical triangle, Napier’s rule. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

GEODETTIC SURVEYING AND THEORY OF ERRORS

Geodetic Surveying: Principle and Classification of triangulation system, Selection of base line and stations, Orders of triangulation, Triangulation figures, Reduction to Centre, Selection and marking of stations Theory of Errors: Introduction, types of errors, definitions, laws of accidental errors, laws of weights, theory of least squares, rules for giving weights and distribution of errors to the field observations, determination of the most probable values of quantities. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

INTRODUCTION TO PHOTOGRAMMETRY: Photogrammetric terms, applications, advantages, limitations and a brief history, types of camera: metric vs. non-metric, types of photogrammetry.

AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY: Geometry of vertical / near-vertical aerial photographs: Orthographic vs. perspective projection, Map vs. photograph, scale of photograph, estimate the scale, relief displacement and its determination, parallax in photographs and measurement, stereoscopy.

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

08 hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15

2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. 'Surveying' Vol 2 and Vol 3 - B. C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications.
2. 'Plane Surveying' A. M. Chandra – New age international (P) Ltd.
3. 'Higher Surveying' A.M. Chandra New age international (P) Ltd.

REFERENCES

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schimidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
2. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
3. Surveying, Arther Bannister et al., Pearson Education, India.

4th Semester B. Tech
CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY AND GREEN MATERIALS

Sub Code :	21SCV45	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3T	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
Mode of delivery:	PBL	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Understand properties of concrete and types of concrete.
2. Know the procedure to determine the properties of fresh and hardened of concrete.
3. To understand factors affecting the strength, workability and durability of concrete.
4. Gain ideas on non-destructive testing of concrete and to impart the methods of proportioning of concrete mixtures.
5. Gives ideas on the construction and inspection requirements the buildings.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to describe about composition and characteristics of Portland cement.

CO2: Able to classify the aggregate and their various properties.

CO3: Able to identify the various properties of concrete and analyzing its workability.

CO4: Able to illustrate design philosophies.

CO5: Able to understand various factors affecting the durability of infrastructures.

MODULE 1

CEMENT– Cement manufacturing process, steps to reduce carbon footprint, chemical composition and their importance, hydration of cement, types of cement. Testing of cement.

WATER – Qualities of water.

CHEMICAL ADMIXTURES –Plasticizers, accelerators, retarders and air entraining agents.

MINERAL ADMIXTURES– Pozzolanic and cementitious materials, Fly ash, GGBS, silica fumes, Met kaolin and rice husk ash.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

FRESH CONCRETE

WORKABILITY-factors affecting workability. Measurement of workability–slump, Compaction factor and Vee Bee Consistometer tests, flow tests. Segregation and bleeding. Process of manufacturing of concrete- Batching, Mixing, Transporting, Placing and Compaction. Curing– Methods of curing – Water curing, membrane curing, steam curing, accelerated curing, self-curing. Good and Bad practices of making and using fresh concrete and Effect of heat of hydration during

mass concreting at project sites.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

CONCRETE MIX PROPORTIONING

Concept of Mix Design with and without admixtures, variables in proportioning and Exposure conditions, Selection criteria of ingredients used for mix design, Procedure of mix proportioning. Numerical Examples of Mix Proportioning using IS-10262-2009.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

HARDENED CONCRETE PROPERTIES: Factors influencing strength, W/C ratio, gel/space ratio, Maturity concept, testing of hardened concrete, creep –factors affecting creep. Shrinkage of concrete – plastic shrinking and drying shrinkage, Factors affecting shrinkage.

CONCEPT OF GREEN BUILDINGS: Green building initiatives, its origin, characteristics of a green building, green buildings in India, certification of green buildings rating systems (BREEAM, USGBC, LEED, IGBC, TERI-GRIHA,) criteria for rating, sustainability.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

GREEN BUILDING MATERIALS: Depleting natural resources of building materials; renewable and recyclable resources; energy efficient materials; green cement, biodegradable materials, smart materials, engineering evaluation of these materials.

DESIGN OF GREEN BUILDINGS: Sustainable sites, impact of building on environment, life cycle assessment. Design on Bioclimatic and solar passive architecture, considerations of energy consumption, water use, and system reliability, indoor air quality, noise level, comfort, cost efficiency in building design.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study / Cost Estimation / Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Neville A.M. “Properties of Concrete”, 4th Ed., Longman.
2. M.S. Shetty, Concrete Technology - Theory and Practice Published by S. Chand and Company, New Delhi.
3. Kumar Mehta. P and Paulo J.M. Monteiro “Concrete-Microstructure, Property and Materials”, 4th Edition, McGraw Hill Education, 2014.
4. A.R. Santha Kumar, “Concrete Technology”, Oxford University Press, New Delhi (New Edition).

REFERENCES

1. M L Gambir, “Concrete Technology”, McGraw Hill Education, 2014
2. N. V. Nayak, A. K. Jain Handbook on Advanced Concrete Technology, ISBN: 978-81-8487-186-9
3. Job Thomas, “Concrete Technology”, CENGAGE Learning, 2015
4. IS 4926 (2003): Code of Practice Ready-Mixed Concrete [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
5. Criteria for RMC Production Control, Basic Level Certification for Production Control of Ready Mixed Concrete – BMTPC
6. Tropical housing and buildings climate design (1973). By Koenig’s Berger Ltd, Ingeesle, T- G Alan Mayhew, S Zokoloy S.V. University Press (India) Pvt. Ltd, Hyderabad.

**4TH Semester B. Tech
EARTH SCIENCE LAB**

Sub Code : 21SCVL46
Hrs/ Week : IT+2L

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2

Credits : 2
Mode of delivery: BM

Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. At the end of this course the students will be able to understand the physical and chemical properties of the Minerals.
2. At the end of this course the students will be able to understand the physical and chemical properties of Rocks.
3. To understand the thickness of the beds, dip and strike of beds, and borehole problems.
4. Based on this, civil engineers can choose the types of foundations and other related aspects.
5. Interpret the knowledge of geological maps for various sites.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the importance and uses of minerals.

CO2: Able to understand the importance and uses of rocks and engineering uses.

CO3: Able to understand the interpretation of geological maps and their Civil Engineering structures.

CO4: Able to understand various techniques to analyze and to make possible solutions for various Geological Engineering problems.

CO5: Able to find out dip and strike of the geological formation to select suitable site.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. Describe and identify the minerals based on their physical, special properties, chemical composition and uses. Study of important rock forming minerals.
2. Describe and identify the rocks as per their by giving their physical properties and engineering uses.
3. Study of Geological maps and their sections: interpreting them in terms of selecting the sites for various civil engineering structures
4. Dip and strike (surface method) problems: To find out the dip and strike of the geological formation to select suitable site for civil engineering structures.
5. Borehole problems (sub surface dip and strike): three point level ground methods.
6. Thickness of strata (out crops) problems: To determine the true thickness, vertical thickness and the width of the out crops on different topographical terrain.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Text book of Geology by P.K. Mukerjee, World Press Pvt. Ltd. Kolkatta.

2. Foundations of Engineering Geology, by Tony Waltham (3rdEd.) Universities Press.
3. Structural Geology (3rd Ed.) by M. P. Billings, Published by Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi
4. Text of Engineering and General Geology by Parbin Singh, Published by S. K. Kataria and Sons, New Delhi.
5. Rock Mechanics for Engineers by Dr. B.P.Verma, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi.
6. Engineering Geology for Civil Engineering by D. Venkata Reddy, Oxford and IBH Publishing Company, New Delhi.
7. Ground water geology by Todd D.K. John Wiley and Sons, New York.

REFERENCES

1. Remote sensing Geology by Ravi P Gupta, Springer Verilag, New York.
2. Physical Geology by Arthur Holmes, Thomson Nelson and Sons, London.
3. Environmental Geology by K. S. Valdiya, Tata McGraw Hills.
4. A text book of Engineering Geology by Chenna Kesavulu, MacMillan India Ltd.
5. Remote sensing and GIS by M. Anji Reddy.
6. Ground water assessment, development and management by K.R. Karanth, Tata McGraw Hills.

**4TH Semester B. Tech
FLUID MECHANICS LAB**

Sub Code : 21SCVL47
Hrs/ Week : 2L
Credits : 1
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 25
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 25
Total Hours : 30

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To understand the flow measurement in a pipe flow
2. To determine the energy loss in pipe flow
3. To study the characteristics of turbines
4. To study the characteristics of pumps
5. To measure the discharge in an open channel flow

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to measure discharge in pipes.

CO2: Able to determine the energy loss in conduits.

CO3: Able to demonstrate the characteristics curves of pumps.

CO4: Able to demonstrate the characteristics curves of turbines.

CO5: To carry out discharge measurements in open channel.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. Calibration of pressure gauge (dead weight method)
2. Calibration of 90° V-notch
3. Calibration of Rectangular and Cipolletti notch
4. Calibration of Broad- crested weir
5. Calibration of Venturiflume
6. Calibration of Venturimeter
7. Determination of Darcy's friction factor for a straight pipe
8. Determination of Hydraulic coefficients of a vertical orifice
9. Determination of vane coefficients for a flat vane & semicircular vane
10. Performance characteristics of a single stage centrifugal pump
11. Performance characteristics of a Pelton wheel
12. Performance characteristics of a Kaplan turbine

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 10 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 10 marks

Viva – voce = 05 marks

Total: 25 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. 'A Text Book of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K.Rajput, S.Chand & Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. 'Principles of Fluid Mechanics and Fluid Machines'- N. Narayana Pillai, Universities Press

(India), Hyderabad, 2009 Edition.

3. 'Fluid Mechanics and Turbo machines'- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.

REFERENCES

1. Experiments in Fluid Mechanics – Sarbjit Singh, PHI Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi, 2009-12-30.
2. Hydraulics and Hydraulic Machines Laboratory Manual – Dr. N. Balasubramanya.

PART-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme - 2

Subject Code	21SQA48	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic

mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations. Domain specific training in respective branches with tests.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A

Percentages, Simple interest and Compound interest –

- a. Percentages as Fractions and Decimals
- b. Percentage Increase / Decrease
- c. Simple Interest
- d. Compound Interest
- e. Relation between Simple and Compound Interest
- f. Finding CI without using formula

Data interpretation and Data sufficiency –

- a. Data Interpretation – Tables
- b. Data Interpretation - Pie Chart
- c. Data Interpretation - Bar Graph
- d. Data Interpretation - Line Graph
- e. Data Sufficiency

Allegation and Mixture, Ratio and Proportion, Partnerships –

- a. Basic Concept of Allegation and Mixture
- b. concept of mixture containing more than two Ingredients
- c. Concept and Problem solving technique in Ratio and Proportion
- d. Partnership "

Permutation, Combination and Probability –

- a. Fundamental Counting Principle
- b. Permutation and Combination
- c. Computation of Permutation
- d. Circular Permutations
- e. Computation of Combination
- f. Probability
- g. Total Probability
- h. Finding Probability without using Combination
- i. Finding Probability using Pascal Triangle

Sentence correction –

- a. Subject Verb Agreement.
- b. Pronoun Reference and Agreement.
- c. Verb Tense.
- d. Modifier.
- e. Parallelism.
- f. Idioms.
- g. Comparisons.
- h. Prepositions.
- i. Determiners.

PART - B

Structural Analysis

Hydrology

Irrigation Engineering

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

4TH Semester B. Tech

ADVANCED SURVEYING LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL49
Hrs/ Week : 2L
Credits : 1
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 25
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 25
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the different methods and techniques of surveying like levelling, compass

survey, contouring and curve settings etc. and their applications in surveying.

CO2: Able to use survey instruments in carrying out survey, to collect data, and write reports and able to perform required calculations to achieve the objective for different types of surveying for different Engineering projects.

CO3: Able to apply the concept of Tacheometry for surveying in difficult and hilly areas to obtain the topographical map of area.

CO4: Able to control the accumulation of errors in projects.

CO5: Able to use modern survey equipment to measure angle and distances.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. Measurement of horizontal angles with method of repetition and reiteration using theodolite, Measurement of vertical angles using theodolite.
2. To set out simple curves using linear methods – perpendicular offsets from long chord and offsets from chords produced.
3. To set out simple curves using Rankine’s deflection angles method.
4. To set out compound curve with angular methods with using theodolite only.
5. Determination of area using Total station
6. Traversing using Total Station
7. Contouring Using Total Station
8. Determination of remote height using total station
9. Stake out using Total Station
10. Distance, gradient, difference in height between 2 inaccessible points

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method			
Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	02
5	Attendance	As per guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

[Converting marks to 25 while reporting to Registrar (Evaluation)]

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation / Result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation / Result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

TEXT BOOKS

1. Surveying, Vol.-1, B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. Plane Surveying, Vol-1-A.M. Chandra, New Age International ® Ltd.
3. Plane Surveying – ALAK, S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
2. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
3. Surveying Vol. I, S.K. Duggal.

INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	21SQA40	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Have exposure on the latest development
- CO2: Acquire new skills
- CO3: Become Industry ready
- CO4: Have more confidence
- CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method

Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MANGALURU
ADDITIONAL MATHEMATICS - II
(Mandatory Learning Course: Common to All Branches)
(A Bridge course for Lateral Entry students of IV Sem. B. Tech.)

Course Title: Additional Mathematics - II
Contact Hours/Week : 02
Total Hours: 25
Exam. Marks : 50

Course Code : 21SMADIP401
L-T-P : 2-0-0
Exam. Hours : 02
Credits : 00

Course Objectives

The mandatory learning course **21SMADIP401** viz., **Additional Mathematics-II** aims to provide essential concepts of

1. linear algebra
2. methods of solving first order differential equations
3. introductory concepts of second & higher order differential equations along with methods to solve them
4. Laplace & inverse Laplace transforms

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students are able to,

1. Solve systems of linear equations in the different areas of linear algebra.
2. Solve second and higher order differential equations occurring in of electrical circuits, damped/un-damped vibrations.
3. Describe Laplace transforms of standard and periodic functions.
4. Determine the general/complete solutions to linear ODE using inverse Laplace transforms.
5. Recall basic concepts of elementary probability theory and, solve problems related to the decision theory, synthesis and optimization of digital circuits

MODULE 1

Linear Algebra: Introduction - rank of matrix by elementary row operations - Echelon form. Consistency of system of linear equations - Gauss elimination method. Eigen values and eigen vectors of a square matrix, Examples. **05 hours**

MODULE 2

Finite differences: Forward and backward differences, Newton's forward and backward interpolation formulae, Lagrange's interpolation formula- Problems.

Numerical integration: Simpson's (1/3)th and (3/8)th rules, (without proof) – Problems. **05 hours**

MODULE 3

Higher order ODE's: Linear differential equations of second and higher order equations with constant coefficients. Homogeneous /non-homogeneous equations. Inverse differential operators. **05 hours**

MODULE 4

Laplace transforms: Laplace transforms of elementary functions. Transforms of derivatives and integrals, transforms of periodic function and unit step function-Problems only. **05 hours**

MODULE 5

Inverse Laplace transforms: Definition of inverse Laplace transforms. Evaluation of Inverse transforms by standard methods. Application to solutions of Linear differential equations and simultaneous differential equations. **05 hours**

Question paper pattern:

- **PART A: TEN** multiple choice questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. [01 mark*10 Questions = 10 marks]
- **PART B: TWO** question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. [08 mark*5 Questions = 40 marks]

Text Book:

1. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi, 43rd Ed., 2018

Reference books:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed., 2015.
2. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal: Engineering Mathematics, Laxmi Publishers, 7th Ed., 2010.

5th Semester B. Tech
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS- II

Sub Code : 21SCV51
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. The course provides students with the principles of elastic structural analysis and behavior of indeterminate structures.
2. Classical and modern analysis techniques are introduced to arm the students with the necessary tools to better appreciate the real behavior of structures.
3. To analyze rigid jointed sway frames
4. To understand the structural behavior before and after application of loads.
5. Able to analyze various structures.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand statically indeterminacy and adopt an appropriate structural analysis technique.
- CO2:** To use slope deflection method and rotation contribution method for various civil engineering structures.
- CO3:** Perform basic calculations to determine redundant forces and displacements, appreciate the difference between idealized structures, models and real structures.
- CO4:** To identify determinate, indeterminate, stable and unstable structures.
- CO5:** Possess an understanding of the physical response of structures to various loads and to identify the kinematic indeterminacy of structures.

MODULE 1

SLOPE DEFLECTION METHOD:

Introduction, Sign convention, Development of slope-deflection equations and Analysis of Beams and Orthogonal Rigid jointed plane frames (non-sway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid) **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

MOMENT DISTRIBUTION METHOD:

Introduction, Definition of terms-Distribution factor, Carry over factor, Development of method and Analysis of beams and orthogonal rigid jointed plane frames (non sway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid)

SWAY ANALYSIS:

Analysis of rigid jointed plane frames (sway, members assumed to be axially rigid and kinematic redundancy ≤ 3) by slope deflection and moment distribution methods. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

KANIS METHODS:

Introduction, Basic Concept, Analysis of Continuous beams and Analysis of rigid jointed non-sway plane frames. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

FLEXIBILITY MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS:

Introduction, Development of flexibility matrix for plane truss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements and Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by flexibility method with static indeterminacy. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

STIFFNESS MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS:

Introduction, Development of stiffness matrix for plane truss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements. And Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by stiffness method with kinematic indeterminacy. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Basic Structural Analysis, Reddy C.S. Second Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Publication Company Ltd.
2. Theory of Structures Vol. 2, S.P. Gupta, G.S. Pandit and R. Gupta, Tata McGraw Hill Publication Company Ltd.
3. Structural Dynamics, by M. Mukhopadhyay,
4. Structural Analysis-II - S. S. Bhavikatti, Vikas Publishers, New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Basics of Structural Dynamics and Aseismic Design, by Damodhar Swamy and Kavita, PHI Learning Private Limited.
2. Structural Analysis, D.S. Prakash Rao,, A Unified Approach, University Press.
3. Structural Analysis, 4th SI Edition by Amit Prasanth & Aslam Kassimali, Thomson Learning.

5th Semester B. Tech
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 21SCV52
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To explain what Geotechnical Engineering is and how it is important to civil engineering.
2. To explain how three phase system is used in soil and how are soil properties estimated using three phase system.
3. To explain role of water in soil behavior and how soil stresses, permeability and quantity of seepage including flow net are estimated.
4. To determine shear parameters and stress changes in soil due to foundation loads.
5. To estimate the magnitude and time-rate of settlement due to consolidation.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand the origin of soil and to identify different types of soil and apply the knowledge of soil and rock to judge its behavior and suitability for civil engineering structures
- CO2:** Able To describe Darcy's law for the flow of water through saturated soils; determine the coefficient of permeability and equivalent hydraulic conductivity in stratified soil.
- CO3:** To understand the various physical and engineering characteristics of different types of soil.
- CO4:** Able To calculate seepage, pore water pressure distribution, uplift forces and seepage stresses for simple geotechnical systems.
- CO5:** Able to describe the direct shear test method and concept of slope stability structures.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: History of soil mechanics, Definition, origin and formation of soil. Phase Diagram, Voids ratio, Porosity, Percentage Air Voids, Air content, Degree of saturation, Water content, Specific Gravity of soil solids and soil mass, Densities and Unit weights - Bulk, Dry, Saturated & Submerged and their inter relationships.

INDEX PROPERTIES OF SOIL AND THEIR DETERMINATION: Index Properties of soil- Water content , Specific Gravity, Particle size distribution, Relative Density, Consistency limits and indices, in-situ density, Activity of Clay, Laboratory methods of determination of index properties of soil: Water content (Oven Drying method & Rapid Moisture method), Specific gravity of soil solids (Pycnometer and density bottle method), Particle size distribution, Liquid Limit- (Casagrande and Cone penetration methods), Plastic limit and shrinkage limit.

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

CLASSIFICATION OF SOILS: Purpose of soil classification, Particle size classification – MIT classification and IS classification, Textural classification. IS classification - Plasticity chart and its importance, Field identification of soils.

CLAY MINERALOGY AND SOIL STRUCTURE: Single grained, honeycombed, flocculent and dispersed structures, Valence bonds, Soil-Water system, Electrical diffuse double layer, adsorbed water, base-exchange capacity, Isomorphous substitution. Common clay minerals in soil and their structures- Kaolinite, Illite and Montmorillonite. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

FLOW OF WATER THROUGH SOILS: Darcy's law- assumption and validity, coefficient of permeability and its determination (laboratory and field), factors affecting permeability, permeability of stratified soils, Seepage velocity, Superficial velocity and coefficient of percolation, quick sand phenomena, Capillary Phenomena.

SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Concept of shear strength, Mohr-coulomb theory, conventional and modified failure envelopes, Effective stress concept total stress, effective stress and Neutral stress, Concept of pore pressure, total and effective shear strength parameters, factors affecting shear strength of soils, Sensitivity and Thixotropic of clay. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

COMPACTION OF SOIL: Definition, Principle of compaction, Standard and Modified proctor's compaction tests, factors affecting compaction, effect of compaction on soil properties, Field compaction control – compactive effort & method, lift thickness and number of passes, Proctor's needle, Compacting equipment.

CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Definition, Mass-spring analogy, Terzaghi's one dimensional consolidation theory-assumption and limitations (no derivation), normally consolidated, under consolidated and over consolidated soils, pre-consolidation pressure and its determination by Casagrande's method. Consolidation characteristics of soil (C_c , a_v , m_v and C_v) **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

DETERMINATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH AND CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Measurement of shear parameters- Direct shear test, unconfined compression test, tri axial compression test and vane shear test, Test under different drainage conditions. Laboratory one dimensional consolidation test, Determination of consolidation characteristics of soils-compression index and coefficient of consolidation (square root of time fitting method, logarithmic time fitting method). **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Soil Engineering in Theory and Practice, Alam Singh and Chowdhary G.R. (1994), CBS Publishers and Distributors Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg, Punmia B.C. (2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co., New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Foundation Analysis and Design, Bowles J.E. (1996), 5th Edition, McGraw Hill Pub, New York.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering- Murthy V.N.S. (1996), 4th Edition, UBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. Basic and Applied Soil Mechanics, Gopal Ranjan and Rao A.S.R. (2000), New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
4. Geotechnical Engineering - Venkatrahmaiah C. (2006), 3rd Edition, New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
5. Soil Mechanics - Craig R.F. (1987), Van Nostr and Reinhold Co. Ltd.
6. Principles of Geotechnical Engineering - Braja M. Das (2002), 5th Edition, Thomson Business Information India (P) Ltd., India.
7. Text Book of Geotechnical Engineering- Iqbal H. Khan (2005), 2nd Edition, PHI, India.

5th Semester B. Tech
DESIGN OF RCC STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 21SCV53
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Identify, formulate and solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to different kinds of loading.
2. Follow a procedural knowledge in designing various structural RC elements.
3. Impart the culture of following the codes for strength, serviceability and durability as an ethics.
4. Provide knowledge in analysis and design of RC elements for the success in competitive examinations.
5. To introduce the various philosophies of R.C. design and to study in detail the limit state design of structural elements such as beams, columns and footings.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Understand the design philosophy and principles
CO2: Solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to flexure, shear and torsion
CO3: Demonstrate the procedural knowledge in designs of RC structural elements such as slabs, columns and footings
CO4: Able to prove the cracking in structural concrete members and its calculation
CO5: Able to understand the detailing of RC structural elements.

MODULE 1

GENERAL FEATURES OF REINFORCED CONCRETE: Introduction, Design Loads, Materials for Reinforced Concrete and Code requirements. Design Philosophy – Limit State Design principles. Philosophy of limit state design, Principles of limit states, Factor of Safety, Characteristic and design loads, Characteristic and design strength. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

PRINCIPLES OF LIMIT STATE DESIGN AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF R.C. SECTION: General aspects of Ultimate strength, Stress block parameters for limit state of collapse, Ultimate flexural strength of singly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of doubly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of flanged sections, Ultimate shear strength of RC sections, Ultimate torsional strength of RC sections, Concepts of development length and anchorage, Analysis examples of singly reinforced, doubly reinforced, flanged sections, shear strength and development length. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

DESIGN OF BEAMS: General Specification for flexure design of beams-practical requirements, size of beam, cover to reinforcement-spacing of bars. General aspects of serviceability - Deflection limits in IS: 456 – 2000. Design procedures for critical sections for moment and shears. Anchorages of bars, check for development length, Reinforcement requirements, Slenderness limits for beams to ensure lateral stability, Design examples for simply supported and Cantilever beams for rectangular and flanged sections. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF SLABS: General consideration of design of slabs, Rectangular slabs spanning one direction, Rectangular slabs spanning in two directions for various boundary conditions. Design of simply supported, cantilever and continuous slabs as per IS: 456 – 2000.

DESIGN OF STAIR CASES: General features, types of stair case, loads on stair cases, effective span as per IS code provisions, distribution of loading on stairs, Design of stair cases. With waist slabs.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

DESIGN OF COLUMNS: General aspects, effective length of column, loads on columns, slenderness ratio for columns, minimum eccentricity, design of short axially loaded columns, design of column subject to combined axial load and uniaxial moment and biaxial moment using SP – 16 charts.

DESIGN OF FOOTINGS: Introduction, load for footing, Design basis for limit state method, Design of isolated rectangular footing for axial load and uniaxial moment, design of pedestal.

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

08 hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Limit State Design of Reinforced concrete-by P.C. Varghese, PHI Learning Private Limited 2008-2009
2. Fundamentals of Reinforced concrete Design-by M.L. Gambhir, PHI Learning Private Limited 2008-2009.
3. Reinforced concrete Design-by Pallai and Menon, TMH Education Private Limited,

REFERENCES

1. Reinforced concrete Design-by S.N. Shinha, TMH Education Private Limited,
2. Reinforced concrete Design-by Karve & Shaha, Structures Publishers Pune.
3. Design of RCC Structural Elements S. S. Bhavikatti, Vol-I, New Age International Publications, New Delhi.
4. IS456: 2000 and SP16

5th Semester B.Tech
TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 21SCV54
Hrs / Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exams Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To understand the importance of transportation, road characteristics, highway development and planning.
2. To study the geometric design of highways, highway alignment and surveys to be carried out.
3. To study the basics and design of various components of railway engineering, types and functions of track, junctions and railway stations.
4. To learn about the aircraft characteristics, planning and design of components of airport.
5. To study the importance of tunneling, types of tunnels, drilling, types and components of docks, harbours, various urban transportation systems and Intelligent Transportation Systems.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand the principles of transportation engineering, need, characteristics, operations, planning and schemes provided by State & Central Govt.
- CO2:** Able to collect and analyze the information required for the highway planning and design of highway construction.
- CO3:** Able to carry out the surveys for railways, design of sleepers-ballast-points-crossings.
- CO4:** Able to select suitable site for the airport, to prepare plan and layout of different types of terminals.
- CO5:** Able to select suitable location for the construction of harbour-docks-tunnel, to select appropriate drilling pattern for tunneling, able to demonstrate the fundamentals of Intelligent Transportation Systems.

MODULE 1

PRINCIPLES OF TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING:

Importance of transportation, Different modes of transportation and comparison, Characteristics of road transport, Jayakar committee recommendations and implementation –Central Road Fund, Indian Roads Congress, Central Road Research Institute.

HIGHWAY DEVELOPMENT AND PLANNING: Road types and classification, Road patterns, Planning surveys, Saturation system of road planning, Phasing Road Development in India, Salient Features of 3rd and 4th Twenty Year Road Development Plans, Present scenario of road development in India (NHDP & PMGSY) and in Karnataka (KSHIP & KRDC) Road development plan - vision 2021.

08 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration.

MODULE 2

HIGHWAY ALIGNMENT AND SURVEYS: Ideal Alignment, Factors affecting the alignment, Engineering Surveys-Map study, Reconnaissance, Preliminary and Final location & detailed survey.

HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN: Importance, Terrain classification, Design speed, Factors affecting geometric design, Cross sectional elements-Camber- width of pavement- Shoulders, Width of formation- Right of way, typical cross sections.

Sight Distance-Restrictions to sight distance- Stopping sight distance-Overtaking sight distance-overtaking zones- Examples on SSD and OSD- Sight distance at intersections, Horizontal alignment- Radius of Curve- Super elevation – Extra widening. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

INTRODUCTION: Role of railways in transportation, Indian Railways, Selection of Routes, Permanent way and its requirements, Gauges and types, Typical cross sections-single and double line B G track in cutting, embankment and electrified tracks, Coning of wheels and tilting of rails, **Rails**-Functions-requirements—types and sections length-defects-wear-creep.

SLEEPERS AND BALLAST: Functions, requirements, Types, Track fitting and fasteners- Dog spike, screw spike and Pandrol clip, Fish plates, Bearing plates, Tractive resistance and hauling capacity.

POINTS AND CROSSING: Components of a turnout, Details of Points and Crossing, types of switches, Track junctions, Stations and Types, Signaling-Objects and types of signals, Station, Turn table, Fouling mark, level crossing. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 4

INTRODUCTION: Layout of an airport with component parts and functions, Site selection for airport, Aircraft characteristics affecting the design and planning of airport, Airport classification, Runway orientation using wind rose with examples

RUNWAY- Basic runway length-Corrections and examples, Runway geometrics, **Taxiway-** Factors affecting the layout - geometrics of taxiway-Design of exit taxiway with examples, **Visual aids-** Airport marking – lighting-Instrumental Landing System. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

TUNNELS: Advantages and disadvantages, Size and shape of tunnels, Surveying-Transferring centre line, and gradient from surface to inside the tunnel working face, Tunneling in rocks- methods, Tunneling methods in soils-Needle beam, Liner plate, Tunnel lining, Tunnel ventilation, vertical shafts, Pilot tunneling, mucking and methods, drilling and drilling pattern.

HARBOURS: Harbour classifications, Layout with components, Natural phenomenon affecting the design of harbours - wind, wave and tide, currents, Breakwater, Wharf and Quays, Jetties and Piers, Dry dock and wet docks, Slipways, Navigational Aids (Intelligent Transportation Systems). **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each (1 Mark x 10 = **10 Marks**)

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Highway Engineering – S K Khanna and C E G Justo, Nem Chand Bros, Roorkee
2. Highway Engineering - L R Kadiyali, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi
3. Transportation Engineering – K P Subramaniam, Scitech Publications, Chennai
4. Transportation Engineering – James H Banks, Mc.Graw. Hill Pub. New Delhi
5. Railway Engineering - Saxena and Arora, Dhanpat Rai & Sons, New Delhi
6. Indian Railway Track – M M Agarwal, Jaico Publications, Bombay
7. Airport Planning and Design – Khanna Arora and Jain, Nem Chand Bros, Roorkee
8. Docks and Tunnel Engineering – R Srinivasan, Charaotar Publishing House
9. Docks and Harbour Engineering – H P Oza and G H Oza Charaotar Publishing House.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Relevant IRC Codes
2. Specifications & Guidelines for Roads and Bridges - MORTH, IRC, New Delhi
3. Specifications & Guidelines – Ministry of Railways, Ministry of Civil Aviation and DGCA
4. Specifications & Guidelines – Ministry of Shipping and National Maritime Foundation.

5th Semester B. Tech

HYDROLOGY AND IRRIGATION ENGINEERING

Sub Code :	21SCV55	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
Mode of delivery:	RM	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To study occurrence, movement and distribution of water which is a prime resource for development of a civilization
2. To know diverse methods of collecting the hydrological information, which is essential, to understand surface and ground water hydrology
3. To know the basic principles and movement of ground water and properties of ground water flow
4. To know the estimation of floods and flood droughting
5. To know the environment impact and the systems of irrigation.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to understand various techniques and parameters of irrigation
- CO2:** Apply science and engineering fundamentals to solve current problems and to anticipate, mitigate and prevent future problems in the area of water resources management
- CO3:** Able to know the losses of water and factors affecting
- CO4:** Able Systematic understanding of the nature of hydrological stores and fluxes and a critical awareness of the methods used to measure, analyze and forecast their variability; and the appropriate contexts for their application
- CO5:** To know irrigation efficiencies, assessment of water requirements for crops.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION TO HYDROLOGY

Introduction, Hydrologic cycle (Horton's representation). Water budget equation, Precipitation: introduction, forms and types of precipitation, measurement of precipitation (Simon's gauge & Syphon gauge only), selection of rain gauge station. Adequacy of rain gauges, methods of computing average rainfall, interpolation of missing data, Evaporation: Definition, factors affecting, measurement (Class A pan). Evaporation control. Evapo-transpiration: Definition, factors affecting, measurement, estimation (Blaneycriddle method) Infiltration: Definition, factors affecting, measurement (double ring infiltrometer), infiltration indices, and Horton's equation of infiltration. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

HYDROGRAPHS: Definition, components of hydrographs, unit hydrograph and its derivation from simple storm hydrograph, base flow separation, Prepositions of unit hydrograph- problems.

ESTIMATION OF FLOOD & FLOOD ROUTING: Definition of flood, factors affecting flood, methods of estimation (envelope curves, empirical formulae, rational method), Flood routing: Introduction to hydrological routing, relationship of out flow and storage, general storage equation.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

INTRODUCTION TO IRRIGATION

Introduction, necessity for irrigation, advantages and disadvantages of irrigation, scope for irrigation science, types of irrigation, methods of irrigation, sewage irrigation, and supplemental irrigation.

GROUND WATER: WELL IRRIGATION

Introduction, some definitions, types of aquifers, storage coefficient, tube wells, selection of suitable site for tube well, methods for drilling tube wells, open well, methods of lifting water. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

SOIL-WATER-CROP RELATIONSHIP

Introduction, physical properties of soil, soil classification, Indian soils, classes and availability of soil water, maintaining soil fertility, soil-water-plant relationship, limiting soil moisture conditions, depth and frequency of irrigation.

WATER REQUIREMENT OF CROPS

Introduction, crop seasons of India, duty, delta, base period. Relation between duty, delta and base period, factors affecting duty, Consumptive use of water, problems. Irrigation efficiencies. Assessment of irrigation water. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

CANALS

Definition, Types of canals, Alignment of canals, Design of canals by Kennedy's and Lacey's methods - Problems, drawbacks in Kennedy's theory, defects in Lacey's theory, comparison of Kennedy's and Lacey's theories, losses in canals, maintenance of irrigation channels, measurement of discharge of a canal. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Engineering Hydrology – Subramanya. K; Tata McGraw Hill NewDelhi-2008 (Ed)
2. Hydrology - Madan Mohan Das, Mim Mohan Das-PHI Learning private Ltd. New Delhi-2009.
3. A Text Book of Hydrology- Jayarami Reddy, Laksmi Publications, New Delhi-2007 (Ed)
4. Irrigation, water Resources and water power Engineering- P.N. Modi - standard book house, New Delhi.
5. Irrigation and Water Power Engineering – Madan Mohan Das & Mimi Das Saikia; PHIL earning pvy. Ltd. New Delhi 2009 (Ed).

REFERENCES

1. Hydrology & Soil Conservation Engineering - Ghanshyam Das, PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2009 (Ed)
2. Hydrology & Water Resources Engineering – Patra K.C., Narosa Book Distributors Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi, 2008 (Ed)
3. Hydrology & Water Resources Engineering- R.K. Sharma & Sharma, Oxford and Ibh, New Delhi
4. 4. Irrigation Engineering and Hydraulic structures- S. K.Garg, Khanna Publication, New Delhi.

5th Semester B. Tech

COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN OF STRUCTURES LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL56

Hrs/ Week : 1T+2L

Credits : 2

Mode of BM

delivery:

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Understand the Drawing Knowledge and Skills
2. Draw various Civil Engineering structures
3. Interpret the data and information
4. Learn Construction Technical Communication Skills
5. Design Civil Engineering structural members.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to prepare detailed working drawings

CO2: Able to communicate information with Clients and other parties

CO3: Able to prepare designs

CO4: Able to prepare specifications

CO5: Able to work as Designer and Contractor

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

Detailing of RCC Structures

1. Beams – Simply supported, Cantilever and Continuous.
2. Slab – One way, Two way and One-way continuous.
3. Staircase – Doglegged
4. Cantilever Retaining wall
5. Counter Fort Retaining wall
6. Circular Water Tank, Rectangular Water Tank.

Detailing of Steel Structures

1. Connections – Beam to beam, Beam to Column by Bolted and Welded Connections.
2. Built-up Columns with lacings and battens
3. Column bases and Gusseted bases with bolted and welded connections.
4. Roof Truss – Welded and Bolted
5. Beams with Bolted and Welded
6. Gantry Girder

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – Voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. N Krishna Raju, “Structural Design and Drawing of Reinforced Concrete and Steel”, University Press
2. Krishna Murthy, “Structural Design and Drawing – Concrete Structures”, CBS Publishers, New Delhi

REFERENCES

1. SP 34: Handbook on Concrete Reinforcement and Detailing, Bureau of Indian Standards
2. IS 13920:2016, Ductile Design And Detailing Of Reinforced Concrete Structures Subjected To Seismic Forces
3. Code Of Practice, Bureau of Indian Standard

5th Semester B. Tech

CONCRETE & HIGHWAY MATERIAL TESTING LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL57

Hrs/ Week : IT+2L

Credits : 2

Mode of RM

delivery:

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Learn the principles and procedures of testing of highway and concrete materials
2. Learn the mix proportions in concrete using IS code
3. Learn quality of materials
4. Learn the specifications of materials
5. Undertake quality aspects of materials.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to know techniques to characterize various pavement materials through relevant tests

CO2: Able to prepare mix design of highway and concrete materials

CO3: Able to draft specifications for concrete and highway materials

CO4: Able to maintain the quality of materials as per Indian Standards

CO5: Able to independently manage the construction works with good quality.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

PART A

CEMENT:

Normal Consistency, Setting time, Soundness by Autoclave method, Compression strength test and Air permeability test for fineness, Specific gravity of cement.

FRESH CONCRETE:

Workability – slump, Compaction factor and Vee Bee tests.

HARDENED CONCRETE:

Compression strength and Split tensile tests. Test on flexural strength of RCC beams, Permeability of concrete.

PART - B

SOIL: CBR Text.

AGGREGATES: Crushing, abrasion, impact and Shape tests (Flaky, Elongation, Angularity number) Specific gravity and water absorption.

BITUMINOUS MATERIALS AND MIXES:

Specific Gravity, Penetration, Ductility, Softening point, Flash and fire point, Viscosity, proportioning of aggregate mixes by Rothfutch Method, Marshall Stability tests.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – Voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Relevant IS Codes and IRC Codes.
2. Highway Material Testing Laboratory Manual by Khanna S Kand Justo, CEG Nemi Chand & Bros.
3. M. L. Gambhir: Concrete Manual, Dhanpat Rai & sons New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Veeraragavan, S.K Khanna and C.E.G. Justo, Highway Engineering, Nem Chand & Brothers, 2014.
2. “Soil Mechanics & Foundation Engg”, Dr. B.C. Punmia, Ashok Kumar Jain, Arun Kumar Jain, Laxmi Publications (P).

**5TH Semester B.Tech
INTERNSHIP - 1**

Sub Code : 21SCV58
Hrs/ Week : 6
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: ---
Total Marks : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their internship area / topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

CO1: Present the work done in his/her internship on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the presentation with sound technical knowledge and communication skills.

Instructions:

Following are the guidelines to be followed for the Internship Programme:

1. The Internship Programme duration is of Four weeks.
2. The internship can be carried out in any industry / R and D Organization / Research Institute / Educational institute of repute.
3. The institutions may also suggest the students to enroll for the Internshala platform for free internships as there is MoU with the AICTE for the beneficial of the affiliated Institutions (<https://internshala.com/>)
4. The Examination of Internship will be carried out in line with the University Project Viva-Voce examination.
5. The Department/college shall nominate staff member/s to facilitate, guide and supervise students under internship.
6. The students shall report the progress of the internship to the guide in regular intervals and seek his/her advice.
7. After the completion of Internship, students shall submit a report with completion and attendance certificates to the Head of the Department with the approval of both internal and external guides.

8. There will be 50 marks for CIE (Seminar: 20, Internship report: 20) and 10 marks for Viva - Voce. The minimum requirement of CIE marks shall be 50% of the maximum marks.
9. The internal guide shall award the marks for seminar and internship report after evaluation. He/she will also be the internal examiner for Viva-Voce.
10. The external guide from the industry shall be an examiner for the viva voce on Internship. Viva-Voce on internship shall be conducted at the college and the date of Viva-Voce shall be fixed in consultation with the external Guide. The Examiners shall jointly award the Viva- Voce marks.
11. In case the external Guide expresses his inability to conduct viva voce, the HoD shall appoint a senior faculty of the Department to conduct viva-voce along with the internal guide. The same shall be informed in writing to the concerned Chairperson, Board of Examiners (BOE).
12. The students are permitted to carry out the internship anywhere in India or abroad. The University will not provide any kind of financial assistance to any student for carrying out the Internship.

Scheme of Examination:

Total: 50 marks

5th Semester B. Tech
Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 3

Subject Code	21SQA58	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives: This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART – A

Sentence completion - a. Using sentence clues. b. Using Hints.c. Structure Words.d. Visualize. e. Pro-active thinking. f. Reactive thinking (signpost words, root words, prefix suffix, sentence structure clues).g. Structure Words. h. Elimination.i. Working Backwards.

Verbal classification - a. Familiarity. b. Systematic approach.c. Logical thinking. d. Elimination. e. Practice makes perfect.

Time, Speed and Distance - a. Basics of time, speed and distance b. Relative speed c. Problems based on trains d. Problems based on boats and streams e. Problems based on races.

Average, Problems on Ages Profit and Loss, Discount" - a. concept of Average
 b. Weighted Average c. Problems on Ages(based on average) d. Problems on ages (based on Ratio) e. Concept and Problem solving technique in Profit and Loss f. Successive Discount.

Syllogism and Venn diagrams, Blood Relations - a. Syllogisms b. Venn Diagrams – Interpretation c. Venn Diagrams – Solving d. Basic concept and terminology in Blood Relations e. Option Elimination method in Blood Relation.

Logarithms, Algebra - a. Logarithm concept and problem solving technique b. Different types of Algebraic expressions c. Different types of Algebraic equations.

Verbal reasoning - a. Reading techniques. b. Removing assumptions. c. Managing time. d. Honing analytical skills. e. Practicing the right format. f. Learning from mistakes.

Spotting errors - a. Subject Verb Agreement. b. Right usage of Participles and Infinitives. c. Right usage of Verbs. d. Right usage of Adjectives. e. Checking spelling and punctuation errors.

PART - B

Highway and Traffic engineering

Design of RCC structures

Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering

Bridge, Railways, Airport Engineering

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

**5th Semester B. Tech
MOOC**

Subject Code	21SCVS01	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Improve learnability

CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study

CO3: Develop the skill

CO4: Industry ready

CO5: Have more confidence level

About the Course:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

Assessment Method for MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The Students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.

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- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

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Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weightage	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs & Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

5th Semester B. Tech
INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE 3

Subject Code	21SCV50	IA Marks	-
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method: Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

6th Semester B. Tech
DESIGN & DRAWING OF RCC STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 21SCV61
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To study the stress strain behavior of steel and concrete
2. To understand the concept of working stress and limit state methods
3. To gain the knowledge of limit state design for flexure, shear, torsion, bond and anchorage
4. To understand the behavior of columns subjected to eccentric load and use of interaction diagrams
5. To study the design of various foundation

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to describe about composition and characteristics of Portland cement.
CO2: To classify the aggregate and their various properties.
CO3: Able to identify the various properties of concrete and analyzing its workability.
CO4: To illustrate design philosophies.
CO5: Able to solve problems in context to singly, doubly and flanged Beam.

MODULE 1

20 hours

1. Layout Drawing: General layout of building showing, position of columns, footings, beams and slabs with standard notations.
2. Detailing of Beam and Slab floor system, continuous beams.
3. Detailing of Staircases: Dog legged and Open well.
4. Detailing of Column footings: Column and footing (Square and Rectangle)

MODULE 2

20 hours

1. Design and detailing of Rectangular Combined footing slab and beam type
2. Design and detailing of Retaining walls (Cantilever and counter fort type)
3. Design and detailing of Circular and Rectangular water tanks resting on ground and free at top(Flexible base and Rigid base), using IS: 3370 (Part IV) only.
4. Design and detailing of Simple Portal Frames subjected to gravity loads.(Single bay & Single storey)

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **TWO** questions, Choosing **ONE** full question from each module.

(20 Mark x 2 Questions = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Structural Design & Drawing Reinforced Concrete & Steel- N. Krishnaraju, University Press.
2. Structural Design and Drawing- Krishnamurthy -, (Concrete Structures), CBS publishers, New Delhi. Tata Mc-Graw publishers.

REFERENCES

1. Reinforced Concrete Structures - B.C. Punmia – Laxmi Publishing Co.
2. Reinforced Concrete Design – S.N.Sinha, McGraw Hill Education.

6th Semester B. Tech
ADVANCED GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 21SCV62
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To emphasize the importance of soil investigations including destructive and nondestructive methods
2. To explain how earth pressure theory is important in retaining structure design
3. To explain the concept of bearing capacity and how to estimate the safe bearing capacity for various foundation system including settlement consideration
4. To explain how do select a suitable shallow foundation system for various site conditions and also analysis of different foundation system
5. To explain in what circumstances pile is needed and how do analysis the pile and pile group under various soil conditions

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to carry out soil investigation for any civil engineering construction

CO2: To analyze earth retaining structures for any kind of soil medium.

CO3: Able to estimate bearing capacity using IS code methods.

CO4: Able to design proper foundations for any kind of shallow foundation system.

CO5: Able to estimate pile and pile group capacity for any kind of soil including group efficiency and negative friction.

MODULE

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION:

Importance of exploration program, Methods of exploration: Boring, Seismic refraction method of geophysical exploration, Types of samples - Undisturbed, disturbed and representative samples, Samplers, sample disturbance, area ratio, Recovery ratio, clearance, Stabilization of boreholes - Typical bore log. Number and depth of borings for various civil engineering structures, soil exploration report.

DRAINAGE AND DEWATERING:

Determination of groundwater level by Hvorslev's method, Control of ground water during excavation: Dewatering - Ditches and sumps, well point system, Vacuum method, Electro- Osmosis method.

08 hours

MODULE 2

STRESSES IN SOILS:

Boussinesq's and Westergaard's theories for concentrated, circular and rectangular loads. Comparison of Boussinesq's and westergaard's analysis. Pressure distribution diagrams, Contact pressure, Newmark's chart.

FLOWNETS:

Laplace equation (no derivation) assumptions and limitations only, characteristics and uses of flownets, Methods of drawing flownets for Dams and sheet piles. Estimating quantity of seepage and Exit gradient. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

LATERAL EARTH PRESSURE:

Active and passive earth pressures, Earth pressure at rest. Rankine's and Coulomb's Earth pressure theories—assumptions and limitations, Graphical solutions for active earth pressure (cohesionless soil only) – Culmann's and Rebhann's methods, Lateral earth pressure in cohesive and cohesionless soils, Earth pressure distribution.

STABILITY OF EARTH SLOPES:

Types of slopes, causes and type of failure of slopes. Definition of factor of safety, Stability of infinite slopes, Stability of finite slopes by Method of slices and Friction Circle method, Taylor's stability number, Felineous method. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

BEARING CAPACITY:

Definitions of ultimate, net and safe bearing capacities, Allowable bearing pressure. Terzaghi's and Brinch Hansen's bearing capacity equations -assumptions and limitations, Bearing capacity of footing subjected to eccentric loading. Effect of ground water table on bearing capacity. Field methods of evaluation of bearing capacity - Plate load test, Standard penetration test and cone penetration test. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

FOUNDATION SETTLEMENT:

Importance and Concept of Settlement Analysis, Immediate, Consolidation and Secondary settlements (no derivations, but, computation using relevant formula for Normally Consolidated soils), Tolerance. BIS specifications for total and differential Settlements of footings and rafts.

PROPORTIONING SHALLOW AND PILE FOUNDATIONS

Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the selection of depth of foundation, Factors influencing Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the choice of foundation, Proportioning isolated, combined, strip and mat foundations, Classification of pile foundation, Pile load capacity, Proportioning pile foundation. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Soil Engineering in Theory and Practice - Alam Singh and Chowdhary G.R. (1994), CBS Publishers and Distributors Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg - Punmia B.C. (2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co., New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Foundation Analysis and Design - Bowles J.E. (1996), 5thEdition, McGraw Hill Pub. Co. New York.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering- Murthy V.N.S. (1996), 4th Edition, UBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. Basic and Applied Soil Mechanics- Gopal Ranjan and Rao A.S.R. (2000), New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
4. Geotechnical Engineering- Venkatrahmaiah C. (2006), 3rdEdition New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
5. Soil Mechanics- Craig R.F. (1987), Van Nostrand Reinhold Co. Ltd.
6. Principles of Geotechnical Engineering - Braja M. Das (2002), 5th Edition, Thomson Business Information India (P) Ltd., India.
7. Text Book of Geotechnical Engineering - Iqbal H. Khan (2005), 2nd Edition, PHI, India.

6th Semester B. Tech

HEALTH & SAFETY IN CONSTRUCTION- CORE ELECTIVE- 1

Sub Code : 21SCV631
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Students will be able to recognize and evaluate occupational safety and health hazards in the workplace
2. Determine appropriate hazard controls following the hierarchy of controls.
3. Able to analyze the effects of workplace exposures, injuries and illnesses, fatalities
4. Methods to prevent incidents using the hierarchy of controls,
5. Effective safety and health management systems and task oriented training.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Evaluate workplace to determine the existence of occupational safety and health hazards.

CO2: Identify relevant regulatory and national consensus standards along with best practices that is applicable.

CO3: Select appropriate control methodologies based on the hierarchy of controls.

CO4: Analyze injury and illness data for trends.

CO5: Able to know the importance of different policies and labor act.

MODULE 1

Occupational Hazard and Control Principles: Safety, History and development, National Safety Policy. Occupational safety and Health Act (OSHA), Occupational Health and Safety administration - Laws governing OSHA and right to know. Accident – causation, investigation, investigation plan, Methods of acquiring accident facts, Supervisory role in accident investigation. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

Ergonomics at Work Place: Ergonomics Task analysis, Preventing Ergonomic Hazards, Work space Envelops, Visual Ergonomics, Ergonomic Standards, Ergonomic Programs. Hazard cognition and Analysis, Human Error Analysis – Fault Tree Analysis – Emergency Response - Decision for action – purpose and considerations. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

Fire Prevention and Protection: Fire Triangle, Fire Development and its severity, Effect of Enclosures, early detection of Fire, Classification of fire and Fire Extinguishers. Electrical Safety, Product Safety: Technical Requirements of Product safety. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

Health Considerations at Work Place: Types of diseases and their spread, Health Emergency. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) – types and advantages, effects of exposure and treatment for engineering industries, municipal solid waste. Environment Management Plans (EMP) for safety and sustainability. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

Occupational Health and Safety Considerations: Water and wastewater treatment plants, handling of chemical and safety measures in water and wastewater treatment plants and labs, Construction material manufacturing industries like cement plants, RMC Plants, precast plants and construction sites. Policies, roles and responsibilities of workers, managers and supervisors. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Goetsch D.L., (1999), “Occupational Safety and Health for Technologists, Engineers and Managers”, Prentice Hall.
2. Heinrich H.W., (2007), “Industrial Accident Prevention - A Scientific Approach”, McGraw-Hill Book Company National Safety Council and Associate (Data) Publishers Pvt. Ltd., (1991), “Industrial Safety and Pollution Control Handbook

REFERENCES

1. Colling D.A., (1990), “Industrial Safety Management and Technology”, Prentice Hall, New Delhi.
2. Della D.E., and Giustina, (1996), “Safety and Environmental Management”, Van Nostrand Reinhold International Thomson Publishing Inc.

6th Semester B. Tech

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT - CORE ELECTIVE- 1

Sub Code : 21SCV632

Hrs/ Week : 3T

Credits : 3

Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To ensure that Environmental considerations are addressed properly and incorporated into decision making process.
2. To avoid, minimize or balance the adverse significant bio-physical, social and other relevant effects of developmental projects.
3. To protect the productivity and capacity of natural system and ecological processes with maintain their function.
4. To promote development that is sustainable and optimizes resources use and management opportunities.
5. Interpret options for evaluating environmental and social impacts

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To encourage students to develop their own perspectives on impact assessment and to be able to relate this to other subject areas and to their wider understanding.

CO2: To identify and explore impact assessment fields and approaches.

CO3: To provide students with the knowledge and professional skills necessary to enable them to undertake environmental impact assessment.

CO4: To know importance of decision making.

CO5: To know the importance of artificial infrastructure development.

MODULE 1

Development Activity and Ecological Factors Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Rapid and Comprehensive EIA, EIS, FONSI. Need for EIA Studies, Baseline Information, Step-by-step procedures for conducting EIA, Limitations of EIA. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

Frame work of Impact Assessment. Development Projects – Environmental Setting, Objectives and Scope, Contents of EIA, Methodologies, Techniques of EIA. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

Assessment and Prediction of Impacts on Attributes Air, Water, Noise, Land Ecology, Soil, Cultural and Socio-Economic Environment. EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA.

EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA.

08 hours

MODULE 4

Public Participation in Environmental Decision making. Practical Considerations in preparing Environmental Impact Assessment and Statements.

Salient Features of the Project Activity-Environmental Parameter Activity Relationships – Matrices.

08 hours

MODULE 5

EIA for Water resource developmental projects, Highway projects: Nuclear Power plant projects, Mining project (Coal, Iron ore), Thermal Power Plant, Infrastructure Construction Activities.

08 hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Environmental Impact Analysis-Jain R.K. - Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
2. Environment Impact Assessment - Anjaneyalu. Y.

REFERENCES

1. Guidelines for EIA of Developmental Projects Ministry of Environment and Forests, GOI.
2. Environment Impact Assessment - Larry W. Canter – McGraw Hill Publication.

6th Semester B.Tech

QUALITY ASSURANCE & QUALITY CONTROL IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 21SCV633

IA Marks : 50

Hrs / Week : 3

Exams Hours : 2

Credits : 3

Exam Marks : 50

Mode of Delivery: RM

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Understanding the basic concepts of TQM
2. Develop a thinking towards Quality systems and Thinking.
3. Understand the application and processes of The various Quality Awards and also Know how ISO9000:2000 works
4. Understand Principle of ISO
5. Apply TQM in Construction Projects

COURSE OUTCONES:

CO1: Evaluate the principles of quality management and to explain how these principles can be applied within quality management systems.

CO2: Identify the key aspects of the quality improvement cycle and to select and use appropriate tools and techniques for controlling, improving and measuring quality.

CO3: Critically appraise the organizational, communication and teamwork requirements for effective quality management

CO4: Critically analyze the strategic issues in quality management, including current issues and developments, and to devise and evaluate quality implementation plans

CO5: Can Apply TQM in Construction Projects

MODULE 1

Concept of Quality:

Definition of quality as given by Deming, Juran, Crosby, difference between Quality Control, Quality Assurance (QA/QC), Total quality control (TQC) and Total Quality Management (TQM), Need for TQM in construction industry. Techniques of QA/QC, Organization necessary for implementation of quality, Quality Manual - Contents, and data required, preparation, responsibility matrix, monitoring for quality - PDCA Cycle. Quality aspects in every phase in the life cycle of Construction project.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

MODULE 2

Quality Control tools and Statistical Quality Control:

TQM Tools: An overview, Histogram, Pareto diagram, Fishbone diagram, Quality control chart-

Testing required for quality control of construction material used in RCC Work- destructive and Non destructive Test (NDT).

Statistical Quality Control - Necessity, Benchmarking, Application of dispersion methods in quality control of construction activity. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

MODULE 3

Training and Development of Human Resources:

Training needs assessment, technical and managerial competencies necessary for achieving quality, preparation for training. Training on Project Rework Reduction Tool (PRRT) software, Different aspects of quality – Appraisals, Factors influencing construction quality – Critical, major failure aspects and failure mode analysis. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

MODULE 4

Study of ISO 9004- Quality System Standards:

Purpose of ISO Standards. Difference between ISO 9001 and ISO 9004. Certification process for ISO9001. Certification bodies involved. Eight Principles of ISO - Basic meaning, applying these principles for an effective quality process in the organization. Management support and commitment necessary for achieving implementation for quality system standards. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

MODULE 5

Achieving TQM in Construction Projects:

Advantages, barriers, principles, steps in implementation, seven types of construction defects. Determining cost of poor quality including hidden cost. Quality functions deployment (QFD). Importance of third party quality audits. CIDC CQRA, quality rating systems, customers satisfaction surveys, Non Conformity Reports (NCR), remedial strategy for reducing NCR's.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks:**

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. International Standards Organization – ISO 9001 and ISO 9004
2. Mantri Handbook – A to Z of Construction – Mantri Publications
3. Juran's Quality Handbook – Joseph M. Juran, A. Blanton. Godfrey – Mc Graw Hill International Edition (1998)
4. Probability and Statistics for Engineers – Miller, Freund-Hall, Prentice India Ltd.
5. Quality Control and Total Quality Management, P.L. Jain, Tata Mc Graw Hill Publication.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Juran Frank, J.M. and Gryna, F.M. Quality Planning and Analysis, McGraw Hill, 2001
2. Kwaku.A., Tena, Jose, M. Guevara, Fundamentals of Construction Management and Organisation, Reston Publishing Co., Inc., 1985.

6th Semester B. Tech

REMOTE SENSING AND GIS - CORE ELECTIVE- 1

Sub Code : 21SCV634
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Provide opportunity to analyze data, explore issues, solve problem and evaluate
2. Maximize the efficiency of decision making and planning
3. Apply geospatial technologies for hazard mitigation and management
4. Provide exposure in gaining knowledge on concepts and applications
5. Provide an overview of earth surface features in remote sensing

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Enable to easily manage, reuse, share data, time management and resources.

CO2: Apply basic concepts and to be used in analysis.

CO3: Demonstrate organizational skills in file and database management.

CO4: Apply concepts, methodologies and applications of remote sensing.

CO5: To interpret images and extract information on earth surfaces.

MODULE 1

Geographic Information system concepts and spatial models. Introduction, Spatial information, temporal information, conceptual models of spatial information, representation of geographic information. GIS Functionality – Introduction, data acquisition, preliminary data processing, data storage and retrieval, spatial search and analysis, graphics and interaction. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

Computer Fundamentals of GIS and Data storage, Fundamentals of computers vector/raster storage character files and binary files, file organization, linked lists, chains, trees. Coordinate systems and map projection: Rectangular polar and spherical coordinates, types of map projections, choosing a map projection. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

GIS and remote sensing data integration techniques in spatial decision support system land suitability and multioriteria evaluation, role based systems, network analysis, special interaction modeling, Virtual GIS. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

Introduction, Ideal remote sensing system, basic principles of electromagnetic remote sensing, electromagnetic energy, electromagnetic spectrum, interaction with earth's atmosphere, interaction with earth- surface materials, spectral reflectance of earth surface materials. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

Applications of Remote sensing: applications in land use land cover analysis, change detection, water resources, urban planning, environmental and geological applications. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Principles of GIS - Peter A BurroughReachael A Mc. Donnel - (Oxford).
2. The GIS Book - George B. Korte, P.E. - 5th Edn., Thomson Learning.
3. Remote sensing and image interpretation - Lillesand - (John Wiley and Sons).
4. Geographical Information system: BemhardSen-Wiley publications.
5. GIS and Computer cartography - Christopher Jones - (Longman)

REFERENCES

1. Fundamentals of Remote Sensing – George Joseph, Universities Press, Hyderabad.
2. Introduction to GIS – Kang tsuang Chang – Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi 2009.
3. Geographical Information Science – Narayan Panigrahi, Universities Press, New Delhi 2010.
4. Geographical Information system & Environmental Modeling: Keith C. Clarke, Bradley O Parks, Michel P. Crane, PHI Learning, New Delhi 2009 Edition.
5. Concepts and Techniques of Geographic Information Systems – C.P.Lo. Albert K.W. Yeung, PHI Learning, New Delhi – 2009 2ndEdition., 1999.

6th Semester B.Tech
SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION

Sub Code : 21SCV635
Hrs / Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exams Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

To expose the students to the concepts of sustainability in the context of building and conventional engineered building materials

1. To use and compare relevant codes
2. Exposing the student to concepts of embodied, operational and life cycle energy, minimizing energy consumption by optimal design
3. Learn the principles of planning orientation of buildings and reuse of building materials
4. Acquire knowledge on various aspects of green construction
5. Understand various codal provisions

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify and compare existing energy codes, green building codes and green rating Systems.

CO2: Identify and use construction materials and methods that more easily allow for salvage and re-use of building materials.

CO3: Perform demolition in ways that allow for salvage of re-usable building materials.

CO4: Understand the techniques and benefits of building performance testing, monitoring and metering.

CO5: Identify and make use of techniques for weatherization and sustainable remodeling of existing structures.

MODULE 1

Introduction: Introduction to Green Building, Principles of Green Building – Site aspect, Soil conservation, Vegetation retention, Energy efficiency, Materials and Resources, Water efficiency, Rainwater Harvesting, Grey water gardening, Solid waste management, Solar energy system.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Green Materials

Necessity and importance of sustainable construction materials, Material composition and properties, Production, Storage, Distribution, Testing, Acceptance criteria, Limitations of use, Economic consideration, and recent developments related to the following materials to be studied.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Admixtures in Concrete

Various construction chemicals / admixtures, Fly ash and its use in concrete, GGBS and its use in concrete, Silica fume concrete, Self-compacting concrete, Fiber reinforced plastics and concrete, Light weight concrete, Light weight cement blocks.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration factory visits. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Special Concrete

High performance concrete, Nano Technology in cement concrete, Ferro cement Technology, Crumb modified bitumen rubber, Glenium concrete, Materials used in nuclear containment structures.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration factory visits. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Green Standards

Energy Conservation Building Codes, Indian Green Building Council, Application, Compliance Mechanism, Procedure for erection of Code compliant building, Renewable Energy, Responsibilities and duties - Owners, Empanelled Energy Auditors (Building), State designated agency.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, case study. **10 Hours**

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS / REFERENCE BOOKS :

1. Concrete Technology by Neville
2. Construction Materials, Methods & Techniques (3e) by William P Spence, Yesdee Publication 2012, Pvt. Ltd, Chennai, India

3. Concrete Structure Properties & Materials by Mehta P.K & Manteio P.J.M, Prentice Hall.
4. Concrete Technology by M.S.Shetty, S.Chand Publications
5. Building Materials by M L Gambhir, Neha Jamwal, Tata McGraw Hill Publ.
6. New Building Materials and Construction World magazine
7. Ferro cement Construction Mannual by Dr. D.B.Divekar, 1030, Shivaji Nagar, Model Colony, Pune
8. Civil Engineering and Construction Review magazine
9. Engineering Materials by Dr. S.V.Deodhar

6th Semester B.Tech

PRINCIPLES OF ARCHITECTURE & LANDSCAPING

Sub Code : 21SCV641

IA Marks : 50

Hrs / Week : 3

Exams Hours : 2

Credits : 3

Exam Marks : 50

Mode of Delivery: RM

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To acquaint the students with fundamental knowledge of space and spatial organization
2. Basic aesthetic principles involved in architectural design
3. Approach to conceptualize and develop architectural design.
4. To analyze the massing and circulation in building.
5. To know the historical development in architecture.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to know the fundamental of space and spatial organization

CO2: Able to understand the aesthetic principles of architectural design

CO3: Able to understand the concept of architectural design a systematic approach

CO4: Able to analyze the massing and circulation in building.

CO5: Able to know the historical development in architecture designs.

MODULE 1

ARCHITECTURE, SPACE AND MASS: Introducing Architecture as a profession and role of an Architect, Definition of architecture- elements of architecture - Concept of space, Articulation of form and space (Primary forms, properties of form, transformation of forms – dimensional transformation, subtractive, additive forms, organization of additive forms), Organization of spaces, sense of enclosure, openings in space defining elements. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 2

AESTHETIC COMPONENTS OF DESIGN: Exploration of the basic principles of design such as Proportion, scale, balance, rhythm, contrast, harmony axis, symmetry, hierarchy, datum; Golden proportion, Theories of scale and proportion, Vitruvian theory, Modular man, Relationship between Art and Design with man, space and environment. To be explained with building examples both historical as well as contemporary. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 3

SPATIAL ORGANISATION AND CIRCULATION: Different types of spatial organizations of masses linear, centralized, radial, clustered, grid Organization illustrations of buildings both historical & contemporary. Building approach, building entrance, Configuration of path, Path space relationship. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 4

DESIGN PROCESS: Integration of aesthetics, function and form - Understanding of formative ideas, organization Concepts, and spatial characteristics. Massing and circulation in design analysis of the following buildings: Falling water house & Guggenheim museum by F. L. Wright -Villa Savoye & Chapel of Notre dame Du Haut by Le Corbusier. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 5

Case studies of historical and contemporary site and buildings (Study of spatial organization, form, elementand art). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Architect: A Candid Guide to the Profession, by Roger K. Lewis
2. Understanding Architecture: Its Elements, History, and Meaning by Leland M.Roth, West View Press Place publication.
3. Francis D. K. Ching, Architecture - Form, Space and Order, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1979 (Canada), 1979.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Roger H. Clark, Michael Pause, Precedents in Architecture, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1996
2. K.W.Smithies, Principles of Design in Architecture, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1981
4. Sam F. Miller, Design Process - A Primer for Architectural & Interior Design, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1995
3. Ernest Burden, Elements of Architectural Design – A Visual Resource, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1994
4. V.S.Pramar, Design Fundamentals in Architecture, Somaiya Publications, NewDelhi, 1973.
5. Vitruvius, Translation: Morris, H. M. (1960). The Ten Books on Architecture.

6th Semester B.Tech

BITUMINOUS MIXTURES AND PAVEMENTS

Sub Code : 21SCV642

Hrs / Week : 3

Credits : 3

Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50

Exams Hours : 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To make the student to understand different types of bituminous materials
2. To make the student to understand the various testing methods for bituminous materials
3. To make the student to understand the concepts of mix design methods
4. To make the student to understand the various procedures of bituminous pavement construction
5. To make the student to understand specifications regarding bituminous materials and construction of bituminous pavement.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to determine the proportions of ingredients required for the mix design of both asphalt mixtures and cement concrete.

CO2: Able to characterize the pavement materials including soil, aggregate, asphalt, cement, asphalt mixtures, cement concrete.

CO3: Able to select appropriate asphalt binder for construction of a flexible pavement depending upon the traffic and climatic conditions.

CO4: Able to choose appropriate stabilization technique for pavement

CO5: Able to design bituminous pavement as per the specifications and standards.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Bituminous Materials, Bitumen sources and manufacturing, Chemistry of bitumen, bitumen structure, Rheology of bitumen, Processing of petroleum crude, Bituminous binders - types, characteristics, test protocols, and recent developments in binder modifications. Elastic modulus, Dynamic modulus, visco-elastic and fatigue properties, creep test, stiffness modulus of bitumen mixes. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Aggregates - Production, Properties, Test methods, Grading, and Blending.

Resilient, Diametral Resilient and Complex (Dynamic) Moduli of Bituminous Mixes, Permanent Deformation Parameters and other Properties. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Bituminous Mixtures - Types, Characteristics, Mix Design methods, and Tests.

Modified Bitumen: Crumb Rubber Modified bitumen, Natural rubber modified bitumen, polymer modified bitumen. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Introduction to Emulsified Bitumen and its characterization: Long term and short term ageing and its effect on bitumen performance, Tests to simulate ageing of bitumen viz. RTFOT and PAV.

Desirable properties of bituminous mixes, Design of bituminous mixes: Modified Marshall's specifications, Hubbard Field method of mix design, Hveem's method of mix design; Introduction to super pave mix design procedure. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Bituminous Pavement Construction - mixture production, transportation, placement, compaction and finishing operation.

Bituminous Pavements - different bituminous layers, and specifications. Hot Mix Asphalt Materials, Mixture Design and Construction. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Bituminous Road Construction in India, by P.S.Kandhal, PHI Learning Private Limited; Revised edition, 2016.
2. Relevant Standards and Guidelines published by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) and the American Standard for Testing and Materials (ASTM) International..
3. Third Edition, National Asphalt Pavement Association, Research and Education Foundation, Lanham, Maryland, 2009.
4. Atkins, N. Harold, Highway Materials, Soils and Concretes, Fourth Edition, 2002, PrenticeHall.
5. Kerbs Robert D. and Richard D. Walker, Highway Materials, McGraw-Hill, 1971.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Relevant IRC and IS Codes of Practices (Separate List will be given).
2. Read, J. And White oak, D., "The Shell Bitumen Handbook", Fifth edition, Shell Bitumen, Thomas Telford Publishing, London 2003

6th Semester B. Tech

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS - CORE ELECTIVE- 2

Sub Code : 21SCV643
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To study the strain –displacement and linear constitutive relation.
2. To understand the numerical techniques applied in FEM.
3. Establishment of element stiffness and load vector.
4. To study about the 2-D iso-parametric concepts.
5. To analyze the 2-D frame elements using FEM techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Demonstrate the differential equilibrium equations and their relationship.

CO2: Apply numerical methods to FEM.

CO3: Demonstrate the displacement models and load vectors.

CO4: Compute the stiffness matrix for isoperimetric elements.

CO5: Analyze plane stress and plane strain problems.

MODULE 1

Basic concepts of elasticity - Kinematic and Static variables for various types of structural problems - approximate method of structural analysis - Rayleigh - Ritz method - Finite difference method - Finite element method. Variation method and minimization of Energy approach of element formulation. Principles of finite element method - advantages & disadvantages - Finite element procedure.

08 hours

MODULE 2

Finite elements used for one, two & three-dimensional problems - Element aspect ratio - mesh refinement vs. higher order elements - Numbering of nodes to minimize band width. Nodal displacement parameters - Convergence criterion - Compatibility requirements - Geometric invariance - Shape function - Polynomial form of displacement function.

08 hours

MODULE 3

Generalized and Natural coordinates - Lagrangian interpolation function - shape functions for one, two & three-dimensional elements. Isoparametric elements - Internal nodes and higher order elements - Serendipity and Lagrangian family of Finite Elements - Sub parametric and Super parametric elements - Condensation of internal nodes - Jacobian transformation Matrix.

08 hours

MODULE 4

Development of strain - displacement matrix and stiffness matrix, consistent load vector, numerical integration. Application of Finite Element Method for the analysis of one & two-dimensional problems - Analysis of simple beams and plane trusses. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

Application to plane stress / strain / axisymmetric problems using CST & Quadrilateral Elements. Application to Plates & Shells- Choice of displacement function (C, C and C type) - Techniques for Non - linear Analysis. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Krishnamoorthy C S, "Finite Element Analysis"- Tata McGraw Hill
2. Desai C and Abel J F, "Introduction to the Finite Element Method"- East West Press Pvt. Ltd., 1972
3. Bathe K J, "Finite Element Procedures in Engineering Analysis"- Prentice Hall
4. Rajasekaran. S, "Finite Element Analysis in Engineering Design"-Wheeler Publishing

REFERENCES

1. Cook R D, Malkan D S & Plesta M.E, "Concepts and Application of Finite Element Analysis" - 3rd Edition, John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1989.
2. Shames I H and Dym C J, "Energy and Finite Element Methods in Structural Mechanics"- McGraw Hill, New York, 1985.

6th Semester B.Tech

GROUND WATER DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT

Sub Code : 21SCV644

IA Marks : 50

Hrs / Week : 3

Exams Hours : 2

Credits : 3

Exam Marks : 50

Mode of Delivery: RM

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To understand the distribution of ground water and water resources systems
2. To develop skills in the ground water flow, type of aquifer and yield from the well
3. To understand methods of ground water exploration
4. To understand water conservation techniques
5. To make student to understand ground water legislation

COURSE OUTCONES:

CO1: Able to understand the ground water movements

CO2: Able to conduct the various tests for ground water

CO3: Able to understand geophysical techniques

CO4: Able to understand the various water conservation techniques

CO5: Able to understand the ground water litigation, planning and management.

MODULE 1

Surface and Ground water Resources

Hydrologic Cycle, Global water resources and Indian Water resources, Surface Water Resources, Water Balance, Available Renewable Water Resources, Water Scarcity, Water Balance as a Result of Human Interference, Groundwater Resources, Types of Aquifers, Groundwater as a Storage Medium, Ground water exploration- Geophysical techniques RS, GIS, GPS. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Construction of wells, Springs. Ground water recharge, Rain Water harvesting, Water conservation techniques. Pump Test and Recovery Test, Thei's, Theim's, Jacob's equations.

Ground water quality, Ground water pollution, Environmental issues. Ground water budget, Ground water management. Ground water legislation. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Ground Water Resources Planning and Management

Necessity, System components, planning scales, Approaches, planning and management aspects, Analysis, Models for impact prediction and evaluation, Post Planning and management Issues.

Ground Water Harvesting and Conservation

Water Harvesting Techniques – Micro-catchments, Design of Small Water Harvesting Structures – Farm Ponds – Percolation Tanks, Yield from a Catchment, Rain water Harvesting-various techniques related to rural and urban area. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Definition of Integrated Water Resources Management, Principles, Implementation of Integrated Water Resources Management, Legislative and Organizational Framework, Types and Forms of Private Sector Involvement. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Water Governance and Water Policy

Legal Framework of Water, Substance of National Water Laws Other key issues, Changing incentives through Regulation, National Water Policy, National Level Commissions, Irrigation Management, Transfer Policies and Activities – Legal Registration of WUAs – Legal Changes in Water Allocation, Role of Local Institutions, Community Based Organizations, Water Policy Reforms: India. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. K. Subramanya, “Engineering Hydrology”, Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishers, New Delhi.
2. H.M. Raghunath, “Ground Water”, Wiley Eastern Publication, New Delhi.
3. Daniel P. Loucks and Eelco van Beek, “Water Resources Systems. Planning and Management”, UNESCO Publication.
4. Mollinga, P. et al, “Integrated Water Resources Management”, Water in South Asia Volume I, Sage Publications, 2006.
5. Todd D. K, Ground water hydrology, 3rd edition, Wiley, 2008.
6. Walton, W. C., Ground water resource evaluation. McGraw Hill, 1970.

REFERENCES:

1. Karanth, K. Groundwater Assessment and Management, Tata McGraw Hill, 2007.
2. Raghunath, H. M, Ground water, New Age International, 3rd edition, 1998.

3. Singh, Chhatrapati “Water Rights in India,” Ed: Chhatrapati Singh. Water Law in India: The Indian Law Institute, New Delhi, 1992.
4. DhruvaNarayana, G. Sastry, V. S. Patnaik, “Watershed Management”, CSWCTRI, Dehradun, ICAR Publications, 1997.

6th Semester B. Tech

GROUND IMPROVEMENT TECHNIQUE - CORE ELECTIVE- 2

Sub Code : 21SCV645
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Understand the fundamental concepts of ground improvement techniques.
2. Apply knowledge of mathematics, Science and Geotechnical Engineering to solve problems in the field of modification of ground required for construction of civil engineering structures.
3. Understand the concepts of chemical compaction, grouting and other miscellaneous methods.
4. Impart the knowledge of geosynthetics, vibration, grouting and Injection.
5. Educate students with numerous ground improvement principles and methods to overcome the problems related to soil on site.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the problematic soil.

CO2: Able Suggest the appropriate ground improvement technique as per the requirement of the project (dewatering, densification, stabilization, swelling control etc.).

CO3: Analyze and design the technique for ground improvement.

CO4: Learn how to change the properties of soil to overcome these problems by modifying the soil and by suitable interventions with the soil.

CO5: Able to understand the types of grouts, equipment's and machinery.

MODULE 1

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GROUND: Introduction, Formation of Rock, soil and soil profile, Soil distribution in India, Alterations of ground after formation, Reclaimed soils, Natural offshore deposits; Ground Improvement Potential – Hazardous ground conditions, poor ground conditions, favorable ground conditions, Alternative Approaches, Geotechnical processes.

COMPACTION: Introduction, compaction mechanics, Field procedure, surface compaction, Dynamic Compaction, selection of field compaction procedures, compaction quality control.

08 hours

MODULE 2

DRAINAGE METHODS: Introduction, Seepage, filter requirements, ground water and seepage control, methods of dewatering systems, Design of dewatering system including pipe line effects of dewatering. Drains, different types of drains.

PRECOMPRESSION AND VERTICAL DRAINS: Importance, Vertical drains, Sand drains, Drainage of slopes, Electro kinetic dewatering, Preloading.

08 hours

MODULE 3

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-I: Definition, cement stabilization, sandwich technique, admixtures. Hydration – effect of cement stabilization on permeability, Swelling and shrinkage and strength and deformation characteristics. Criteria for cement stabilization. Stabilization using Fly ash.

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-II: Lime stabilization – suitability, process, criteria for lime stabilization. Other chemicals like chlorides, hydroxides, lignin and hydrofluoric acid. Properties of chemical components, reactions and effects. Bitumen, tar or asphalt in stabilization. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

VIBRATION METHODS: Introduction, Vibro compaction– blasting, vibratory probe, Vibro displacement compaction – displacement piles, vibroflotation, sand compaction piles, stone columns, heavy tamping.

GROUTING AND INJECTION: Introduction, Effect of grouting. Chemicals and materials used. Types of grouting. Grouting procedure, Applications of grouting. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

GEOSYNTHETICS: Introduction, Geosynthetic types, properties of Geosynthetics – materials and fibre properties, Geometrical aspects, mechanical properties, Hydraulic properties, Durability; Applications of Geosynthetics - Separation, Filtration and Fluid Transmission, Reinforcement.

MISCELLANEOUS METHODS (ONLY CONCEPTS & USES): Soil reinforcement, Thermal methods, Ground improvement by confinement – Crib walls, Gabions and Mattresses, Anchors, Rock bolts and soil nailing. Stone Column, Micro piles. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Ground Improvement Techniques- Purushothama Raj P.(1999) Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. Construction and Geotechnical Method in FoundationEngineering- Koerner R.M. (1985) - McGraw Hill Pub. Co.,New York.

REFERENCES

1. Engineering principles of ground modification- Manfred Hausmann (1990) - McGraw Hill Pub. Co., New York.
2. Methods of treatment of unstable ground- Bell, F.G. (1975) Butterworths, London.
3. Expansive soils- Nelson J.D. and Miller D.J. (1992) -, John Wiley and Sons.
4. Soil Stabilization; Principles and Practice- Ingles. C.G. and Metcalf J.B. (1972) - Butterworths, London.

6th Semester B. Tech
BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE

Sub Code : 21SBM651
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 45

Course Objectives:

- To provide students with solid understanding of IT role at the enterprise.
- Modern information systems dedicated for both data collection and knowledge discovery will provide management with an easy and understandable toolkit for online operations control over a scaling business in a diverse environment.
- Provides an overview of BI and demonstrates how it facilitates effective implementation of organizational strategies through better business decision making.

Course Outcomes:

On Completion of this course the students are able to,

CO1: Describe the concepts and components of Business Intelligence.

CO2: Critically evaluate use of BI for supporting decision making in an organization.

CO3: Understand and use the technologies and tools that make up BI (OLAP).

CO4: Understand and design the technological architecture that underpins BI systems.

CO5: Plan the implementation of a BI system.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Business Intelligence: Understanding the scope of today's BI solutions and how they fit into existing infrastructure Assessing new options such as SaaS and cloud-based technology. Describe BI, its components & architecture, previewing the future of BI Crafting a better experience for all business users, End User Assumptions, setting up Data for BI, The Functional Area of BI Tools, Query Tools and Reporting, OLAP and Advanced Analytics, Supporting the requirements of senior executives, including performance management.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 2

Elements of Business Intelligence Solutions: Reports & ad hoc queries; Analyse OLAP data; Dashboards & Scorecards development, Metadata Models; Automated tasks & events; Mobile & disconnected BI; Collaboration capabilities; Real time monitoring capabilities; Software development kit; Consume BI through portals, web applications, Desktop applications.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 3

Building the BI Project: Planning the BI project, Project Resources; Project Tasks, Risk Management and Mitigation, Cost-justifying BI solutions and measuring success, Collecting User Requirements, Requirements-Gathering Techniques; Prioritizing & Validating BI Requirements, Changing Requirements; BI Design and Development, Best Practices for BI Design; Post-Implementation Evaluations, Maintaining Your BI Environment.
Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 4

Reporting Authoring: Building reports with relational Vs Multidimensional data models; Types of Reports – List, Crosstabs, Statistics, Chart, map, financial etc.; Data Grouping & Sorting, Filtering Reports, Adding Calculations to Reports, Conditional formatting, Adding Summary Lines to Reports. Drill up, drill-down, drill-through capabilities. Run or schedule report, different output forms – PDF, excel, csv, xml etc.
Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 5

BI Deployment, Administration & Security: Centralized Versus Decentralized Architecture, BI Architecture Alternatives, phased & incremental BI roadmap, System Sizing, Measurements and Dependencies, System Sizing, Measurements, and Dependencies. Setting Early Expectations and Measuring the Results. End-User Provisos. OLAP Implementations. Expanding BI Authentication Authorization, Access Permissions, Groups and Roles, Single-sign on Server Administration, Manage Status & Monitoring, Audit, Mail server & Portal integration, Back Up and Restore.
Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2/individual)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
	Total		50

Scheme of Examination for End Semester Examination of 50 Marks:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks.**

Text Books:

1. Business Intelligence (IBM ICE Publication).

Reference Books:

1. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_intelligence.
2. http://www.webopedia.com/TERM/B/Business_Intelligence.html.
3. [Http://www.cio.com/article/40296/Business_Intelligence_Definition_and_Solutions](http://www.cio.com/article/40296/Business_Intelligence_Definition_and_Solutions).

6thSemester B. Tech

INTRODUCTION TO BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

Sub Code : 21SBM652

Hrs/ Week : 3

Credits : 3

Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 45

Course Objectives:

- Describe the context and purpose of business.
- Analyze the business environment, discuss legal forms of business.
- Explain and analyze basics of accounting function, identify the importance of management to business.
- Describe and demonstrate decision-making skills in marketing function, human resource management.

Course Outcomes:

On Completion of this course the students are able to,

CO1: Describe the finance function and its relation to the securities market.

CO2: Describe the role and functions of a manager and management skills.

CO3: Distinguish among primary functions within a business.

CO4: Identify the interests and roles of key business stakeholders.

CO5: Demonstrate a working vocabulary of business terms.

MODULE 1

Nature of Management and its Process Meaning, Objectives, Importance; Nature of Management- Science, Art, Profession; Evolution of Management; Management Functions- Planning, Organising, Personnel Management, Directing and Control; Principles of Management- Fayol and Taylor Principles; Managerial Skills; Task and Responsibilities of Professional Manager.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 2

Planning: Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Planning process; Types of Plans Objectives, Strategy, Policy, Procedures, Method, Rule, Budget; Plan vs. Programme Policies and Procedures; Decision making. **Organizing:** Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Organising process; Types of Organisation; Structure of Organisation; Centralisation and De-Centralisation; Delegation; Growth in Organisation.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 3

Human Resource Management: Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Recruitment process-Selection; Training and Development, Methods; Functions of Personnel Manager; Performance Management; Appraisal Methods; Human Resource Planning,; Talent Management; Organization Development. Direction and Co-ordination Direction: Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Elements of Directing Supervision, Motivation, Leadership, Communication; Co-Ordination-Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Co-Ordination.

Types- Internal and External; Coordination- the Essence of Management.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 4

Controlling: Concept, Features, Importance, Limitations; Control process; Essentials of a Good Control System; Techniques of Control-Traditional and Non-Traditional Control devices; Relationship between Planning and Controlling.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 5

Recent Trends in Management Change Management; Crisis Management; Total Quality Management; Risk Management; Global Practices.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case study	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2/individual)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
	Total		50

Scheme of Examination for End Semester Examination of 50 Marks:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks.**

Text Books:

1. L.M. Prasad Principles and Practice of Management.
2. N.C. Jain, Saakshi Management: Theory and Practice; A.I.T.B.S. Publishers, Delhi.
3. J.P. Mahajan Management – Theory and Practice; Ane Books Pvt. Ltd., Daryaganj, New Delhi-26
4. T. Ramasamy Principles of Management; Himalaya Publishing House

Reference Books:

1. M.C. Shukla Business Organisation & Management; Sultan Chand & Co., New Delhi.
2. Y.K. Bhusan Fundamentals of Business Organisation & Management; Sultan Chand & Co., New Delhi.
3. Singh & Chabra Business Organisation and Management; Kitab Mahal, Allahabad.
4. J.S. Chandan Management: Concepts and Strategies; Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
5. George IT Milkovich Human Resource Management and Jahri W. Boudreau, Chicago
6. Lan Breadwell and Human Resource Management; Macmillan, New Delhi. Lan Holden

6th Semester B. Tech
OPERATIONS RESEARCH

Sub Code : 21SBM653
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 45

Course Objectives:

- To impart knowledge in concepts and tools of Operations Research.
- To understand mathematical models used in Operations Research.
- To apply these techniques constructively to make effective business decisions.
- To introduce quantitative methods and techniques for decision making, model formation and applications.
- Understand the usage of game theory and Simulation for Solving Business Problems.

Course Outcomes:

On Completion of this course the students are able to,

CO1: Be able to understand the characteristics of different types of decision-making environments and the appropriate decision-making approaches and tools.

CO2: Be able to build and solve Transportation models and assignment models.

CO3: To design new simple models like CPM, MSTP.

CO4: Improve decision-making and develop critical thinking and objective analysis of decision problems.

CO5: Be able to implement practical cases by using TORA, WinQSB.

MODULE 1

Introduction to OR: Introduction to OR- Origin, Nature, Definitions, Managerial Applications and Limitations of OR. Linear and Non- Linear, Integer, Goal [Multi- Objective] and Dynamic Programming Problems (Emphasis is on Conceptual Frame Work-no Numerical Problems). Linear Programming: Mathematical Model, Formulation of LPP, Assumptions Underlying LPP, Solution by the Graph and Exceptional Cases.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 2

Linear Programming Problem: LPP – Simplex Method- Solution to LP Problems, Maximization and Minimization Cases, Optimality conditions, Degeneracy. Dual – Formulation, Relationship between Primal, Dual, Solution of Dual.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 3

Transportation Problem and Assignment Problem: Transportation Problem (TP) - Mathematical Model, IBFS using Northwest Corner Rule, Row and Column Minimum Methods, Matrix Minimum (Low-Cost Entry) Method and Vogel's Approximation Method, Unbalanced TP, Degeneracy, Optimality Test and Managerial Applications. Assignment Problem (AP): Mathematical Model, Unbalanced AP, Restricted AP, Method of Obtaining Solution- Hungarian Method.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 4

Network Fundamentals: Network Fundamentals- Scheduling the Activities -Fulkerson's Rule – CPM- Earliest and Latest Times - Determination of Earlier Starting Time and Earliest Finishing Time in the Forward Pass – Latest Starting Time and Latest Finishing Time in Backward Pass, Determination of Critical Path, Crashing, Time Cost Trade Off, PERT Beta Distribution, Probabilistic Models, Calculation of CP.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 5

Applications of OR: Queuing Theory, Concepts of Queue/Waiting Line, General Structure of a Queuing system, Operating Characteristics of Queues, deterministic Queuing Models, Probabilistic Queuing Model, Cost Analysis. Single Channel Queuing Model, Poisson Arrival and Exponential Service Times with Infinite Population. Game Theory, Concepts, Saddle Point, Dominance, Zero-Sum Game, Two, Three and More Persons Games, Analytical Method of Solving Two Person Zero Sum Games, Graphical Solutions for (m x 2) and (2 x n) Games.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2/individual)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
		Total	50

Scheme of Examination for End Semester Examination of 50 Marks:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks.**

Text Books:

1. Hillier, Frederick S. & Lieberman, "Introduction to Operations Research Concepts and Cases", 2010, 8th Ed. TMH
2. N.D. Vohra, "Quantitative Techniques in Management", 2010, 4th Ed. TMH.
3. J.K. Sharma, "Operations Research Theory and Applications 2009, 4th Ed. McMillan.

Reference Books:

1. Kasana, HS & Kumar, KD, "Introductory Operations Research theory and Applications", 2008, Springer.
2. Chakravarty, P, "Quantitative Methods for Management and Economics", 2009, 1st Ed. HPH.

6thSemester B. Tech

INTRODUCTION TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Sub Code	: 21SBM654	IA Marks	: 50
Hrs/ Week	: 3	Exam Hours	: 2
Credits	: 3	Exam Marks	: 50
Mode of Delivery:	RM	Total Hours	: 45

Course Objectives:

- To provide students with solid understanding of IT role at the enterprise.
- Modern information systems dedicated for both data collection and knowledge discovery will provide management with an easy and understandable toolkit for online operations control over a scaling business in a diverse environment.
- Provides an overview of BI and demonstrates how it facilitates effective implementation of organizational strategies through better business decision making.

Course Outcomes:

On Completion of this course the students are able to,

CO1: Describe the concepts and components of Business Intelligence.

CO2: Critically evaluate use of BI for supporting decision making in an organization.

CO3: Understand and use the technologies and tools that make up BI (OLAP).

CO4: Understand and design the technological architecture that underpins BI systems.

CO5: Plan the implementation of a BI system.

MODULE 1

Entrepreneurial Perspectives: Introduction to Entrepreneurship – Evolution – Concept of Entrepreneurship – Types of Entrepreneurs -Entrepreneurial Competencies, Capacity Building for Entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial Training Methods – Entrepreneurial Motivations – Models for Entrepreneurial Development – The process of Entrepreneurial Development.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 2

Directing and Controlling: Meaning and nature of directing, leadership styles, motivation Theories, Communication- Meaning and importance, Coordination- meaning and importance, Controlling- meaning, steps in controlling, methods of establishing control

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 3

Management of MSMEs and Sick Enterprises: Challenges of MSMEs, Preventing Sickness in Enterprises – Specific Management Problems; Industrial Sickness; Industrial Sickness in India – Symptoms, process and Rehabilitation of Sick Units. Preparation of project and ERP: meaning of

project, project identification, project selection, project report, need and significance of project report, contents, formulation, guidelines by planning commission for project report,

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 4

Managing Marketing and Growth of Enterprises: Essential Marketing Mix of Services, Key Success Factors in Service Marketing, Cost and Pricing, Branding, New Techniques in Marketing, International Trade. Enterprise Resource Planning: Meaning and Importance- ERP and Functional areas of Management – Marketing / Sales- Supply Chain Management – Finance and Accounting – Human Resources – Types of reports and methods of report generation.

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

MODULE 5

Micro and Small Enterprises: Definition of micro and small enterprises, characteristics and advantages of micro and small enterprises, steps in establishing micro and small enterprises, Government of India industrial policy 2007 on micro and small enterprises, case study (Microsoft), Case study (Captain G R Gopinath), case study (N R Narayana Murthy & Infosys),

Teaching Methodology: Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept. **9 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2/individual)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
		Total	50

Scheme of Examination for End Semester Examination of 50 Marks:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

Text Books:

1. Entrepreneurship Development and Small Business Enterprises, Poornima M. Charantimath, 2e, Pearson, 2014.
2. Entrepreneurship, a South – Asian Perspective, D.F. Kuratko and T. V. Rao, 3rd Ed., Cengage, 2012.
3. Entrepreneurship, Arya Kumar, 4 e, Pearson 2015.
4. The Dynamics of Entrepreneurial Development and Management, Vasant Desai, Himalaya Publishing House, 2015.
5. Dynamics of Entrepreneurial Development & Management -Vasant Desai, Himalaya Publishing House.
6. Entrepreneurship Development -Small Business Enterprises -Poornima M Charantimath Pearson Education – 2006.
7. Management and Entrepreneurship - Kanishka Bedi- Oxford University Press-2017.

Reference Books:

1. Management Fundamentals -Concepts, Application, Skill Development Robert Lusier Thomson.
2. Entrepreneurship Development -S S Khanka -S Chand & Co.
3. Management -Stephen Robbins -Pearson Education /PHI -17th Edition, 2003
4. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_intelligence.
5. http://www.webopedia.com/TERM/B/Business_Intelligence.html.
6. Http://www.cio.com/article/40296/Business_Intelligence_Definition_and_Solutions.

6th Semester B. Tech
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING LAB

Sub Code : 21SCVL66
Hrs/ Week : 1T+2L
Credits : 2
Mode of delivery: BM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To estimate index properties of soils (coarse and fine)
2. To estimate consistency limit of fine grained soils
3. To estimate shear strength of soils by direct shear test, triaxial shear test, vane shear test & unconfined compressive test
4. To estimate the engineering properties of the soils by density test, CBR test permeability test and consolidation test
5. To demonstrate miscellaneous equipment's such as Augers, Samplers, Rapid Moisture meter, Proctor's needle.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To classify soil by physical observation of the soils.
CO2: To classify soil based on estimated index and engineering characteristics of soils.
CO3: To carry out interpolation among the estimated soil design parameters.
CO4: Able to understand different strength test.
CO5: Able to use miscellaneous equipment's.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. Identification of gravel type, sand type, silt type and clay types soils, Tests for determination of Specific gravity (for coarse and fine grained soils) and Water content (Oven drying method).
2. Grain size analysis of soil sample (sieve analysis).
3. In situ density by core cutter and sand replacement methods.
4. Consistency Limits – Liquid Limit (Casagrande and Cone Penetration Methods), plastic limit and shrinkage limit.
5. Standard Proctor Compaction Test and Modified Proctor Compaction Test.
6. Coefficient of permeability by constant head and variable head methods.
7. Strength Tests
 - a) Unconfined Compression Test
 - b) Direct Shear Test
 - c) Triaxial Compression Test (undrained)
8. Consolidation Test- Determination of compression index and coefficient of

consolidation.

9. Laboratory vane shear test
10. Determination of CBR value
11. Demonstrations
 - a. Demonstration of miscellaneous equipments such as Augers, Samplers, Rapid Moisture meter, Proctor's needle.
 - b. Demonstration of Hydrometer Test.
 - c. Demonstration of Free Swell Index and Swell Pressure Test
 - d. Demonstration of determination of relative density of sands.
12. Preparing a consolidated report of index properties and strength properties of soil

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg - Punmia B.C.(2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co. , New Delhi.
2. Soil Testing for Engineers- Lambe T.W., Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Manual of Soil Laboratory Testing- Head K.H., (1986)- Vol. I, II, III, Princeton Press, London.

REFERENCES

BIS Codes of Practice:

1. IS 2720 (Part-3/Sec. 1) – 1987; IS 2720 (Part – 2) - 1973; IS 2720 (Part – 4) – 1985; IS 2720 (Part – 5) – 1985; IS 2720 (Part – 6) – 1972; IS 2720 (Part –7) – 1980;
2. IS 2720 (Part – 8) – 1983; IS 2720 (Part – 17) – 1986; IS 2720 (Part - 10) – 1973; IS 2720 (Part – 13) – 1986; IS2720 (Part 11) – 1971; IS 2720 (Part 15) – 1986; IS 2720(Part 30) – 1987; IS 2720 (Part 14) – 1977; IS 2720 (Part –14) – 1983; IS 2720 (Part – 28) – 1974; IS 2720 (Part – 29) –1966, IS 2720 (Part-60) 1965.

6th Semester B. Tech

EXTENSIVE CIVIL ENGINEERING SURVEYING PROJECT

Sub Code :	21SCVL67	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	2	Exam Marks :	50
Mode of delivery:	RM	Total Hours :	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To know thorough knowledge of the investigation and design of the projects
2. To know the procedure of submission of project report.
3. To impart the design and drawings in AUTO CAED
4. To know the importance of new tank projects
5. To impart the knowledge of water and sewage supply, highway and old tank projects

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to prepare contour map of the given area using different devices.

CO2: Understand field activity which provides real application of theoretical principles of surveying.

CO3: Able to doing simultaneously field work and office work.

CO4: Able to understand the importance of new tank project- estimate the requirement of water for future.

CO5: Able to plan alternate routes, preparation of village maps and details of existing structures.

EXPERIMENTS - 40 hours

1. NEW TANK PROJECTS: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Alignment of center line of the proposed bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the center line.
- c. Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
- d. Design and preparation of drawing with report

2. WATER SUPPLY AND SANITARY PROJECT: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Examination of sources of water supply, Calculation of quantity of water required based on existing and projected population.
- c. Preparation of village map by using total station.
- d. Survey work required for laying of water supply and UGD
- e. Location of sites for water tank. Selection of type of water tank to be provided. (Ground level,

overhead and underground)

f. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report.

3. HIGHWAY PROJECT: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Preliminary and detailed investigations to align a new road (min. 1 to 1.5 km stretch) between two obligatory points. The investigations shall consist of topographic surveying of strip of land for considering alternate routes and for final alignment. Surveying by using total station.
- c. Report should justify the selected alignment with details of all geometric designs for traffic and design speed assumed.
- d. Drawing shall include key plan initial alignment, final alignment, longitudinal section along final alignment, typical cross sections of road.

4. RESTORATION OF AN EXISTING TANK: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Alignment of center line of the existing bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the center line.
- c. Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
- d. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report

5. TOWN / HOUSING / LAYOUT PLANNING: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Detailed survey required for project execution like contour surveys
- c. Preparation of layout plans as per regulations
- e. Centerline marking-transfer of centre lines from plan to ground
- f. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report as per regulations.

NOTE:

- To be conducted between 5th & 6th Semester for a period of 2 weeks including training on total station.
- An extensive project preparation training involving investigation, collection of data is to be conducted. For TWO projects use of Total Station is compulsory.
- The student shall submit a project report consisting of designs and drawings.
- Drawings should be done using CAD and survey work using total station
- Students should learn data download from total station, generation of contours, block leveling, longitudinal and cross sectional diagrams, and capacity volume calculation by using relevant software.
- The course coordinators should give exposure and simulate activities to achieve the course outcomes.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- At the end of the semester, students should submit the Project Report
- Viva Voce and PPT Presentation

TEXT BOOKS

1. Surveying' Vol 2 and Vol 3 - B. C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications.
2. 'Plane Surveying' A. M. Chandra – New age international (P) Ltd.

REFERENCES

1. 'Higher Surveying' A.M. Chandra New age international (P) Ltd

6th Semester B. Tech
Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 4

Subject Code	21SQA68	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A

Clocks, calendars, Direction Sence - a. Concepts on Clocks b. angles between the hand of a clock c. concept of Calendar d. Concept of Leap year, days and datee. Basic concept and Problem solving tecnic for various types of problem in Direction sence"

Critical reasoning- a. Argument – Identifying the Different Parts (Premise, assumption, conclusion)
 b. Types of Questions

Surds, Indices and Simplification - a. Surdsb. Indices c. Simplification exercises

Set Theory - a. Set definition and formulas b. Power set c. Sub set d. Set multiplication

Functions - a. Roots of a function b. Domain and range c. Problems involving multiple functions

Cryptarithmic - Problem solving technique on cryptarithmic

Trigonometry - a. Heights and distance problems b. Identities, angles c. Simplification

Letter and Symbol Series, Visual Sequence, Alpha numeric problems - a. Problem solving technique for Letter and Symbol series b. Visual Sequence c. Alpha numeric problems

Analogy - a. Synonyms/Antonyms b. Object/Purpose c. Source / Product d. Part/Whole.
e. Animal/Habitat. f. Characteristics.

Letter and Email Writing - a. Types (Formal, Informal, Semi-Formal).
b. Formats.
c. Samples.
d. Practice using the right salutations, greetings, subject line, addresses, conciseness and preciseness.

PART –B

Design of steel structures

Construction Management

Pre-stressed concrete

Applied Mechanics and Graphic Statics

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal.

**6th Semester B. Tech
MOOC**

Subject Code	21SCVS02	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Improve learnability
- CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- CO3: Develop the skill
- CO4: Industry ready
- CO5: Have more confidence level

About the Course:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

Assessment Method for MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The Students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.

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- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weightage	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs & Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

6th Semester B. Tech
INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	21SCV60	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Have exposure on the latest development
- CO2: Acquire new skills
- CO3: Become Industry ready
- CO4: Have more confidence
- CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method: Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

7th Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF STEEL STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 21SCV71
Hrs / Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exams Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn IS 800-2007 code of practice for the design of Compression, Tension and Flexural members using various cross-sections
2. To study the behavior and design of compression and tension members using simple and built-up sections
3. Analysis and design of steel members and connections
4. To study the components of truss, loads on trusses, analysis and design of purlins and truss members
5. To study the design of bolted and welded connections.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to apply the IS code of practice for the design of steel structural elements
CO2: Design tension and compression members using simple and built-up sections
CO3: Able to calculate forces on the various members of the truss and design them.
CO4: Able to analyze the behavior of bolted connections and design them
CO5: Able to design welded connections for both axial and eccentric forces.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Advantages and Disadvantages of Steel structures, Loads and Load combinations, Design considerations, Limit State Method (LSM) of design, Failure criteria for steel, Codes, Specifications and Section classification.

BOLTED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Behavior of Bolted joints, Design strength of ordinary Black Bolts, High Strength Friction Grip Bolts (HSFG), Simple Connections, Moment resistant connections, Beam to Beam and Beam to Column connections. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

WELDED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Welding process, Welding electrodes, Advantages of Welding, Types and Properties of Welds, Types of joints, Weld symbols, Weld specifications, Design of welds, Simple joints, Moment resistant connections, Beam to Beam and Beam to Column splices. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

Design of Tension Members: Introduction, Types of tension members, Behavior of tension members, Modes of failure, Factors affecting the strength of tension members, Angles under tension, Splices, Gussets, Problems on Design of tension members. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

Design of Compression Members: Introduction, Failure modes, Behaviour of compression members, Elastic buckling of slender compression members, Sections used for compression members, Effective length of compression members, Design of compression members, Design of built up compression members. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

Plastic Behaviour of Structural Steel: Introduction, Plastic theory, Plastic hinge concept, Plastic collapse load, Theorem of Plastic collapse.

Design of Beams: Introduction, Beam types, Lateral stability of beams, factors affecting lateral stability, Behaviour of simple and built-up beams in bending (without vertical stiffeners), Design strength of laterally supported beams in Bending, Design strength of laterally unsupported beams, Maximum deflection. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Note: Study of this course should be based on IS: 800-2007

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

Text / Reference Books

1. Structural Design & Drawing – N. Krishna Raju, Universities Press, India
2. Design of Steel Structures, N. Subramanian, Oxford, 2008
3. Design of Steel Structures - Negi - Tata McGraw Hill Publishers
4. Limit State Design of Steel Structures, Duggal. TATA Megra Hill 2010
5. Bureau of Indian Standards, IS 800-2007, IS 875-1987
6. Steel Table – Birla Publications, New Delhi.

7th Semester B. Tech

QUANTITY SURVEYING AND VALUATION

Sub Code : 21SCV72
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To know the importance of preparing the types of estimates under different conditions
2. To know about the rate analysis and bill preparations
3. To study about the specification writing
4. To understand the valuation of land and buildings
5. To know the essentials of contract and its legal provisions.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Apply different types of estimates in different situations.
CO2: Able Carry out analysis of rates and bill preparation at different locations.
CO3: Demonstrate the concepts of specification writing.
CO4: Able Carry out valuation of assets.
CO5: Able to know the legal aspects on a breach of contract.

MODULE 1

ESTIMATION: Study of various drawings with estimates, important terms, units of measurement, abstract Methods of taking out quantities and cost –center line method, long and short wall method or crossing method.

Estimating quantities of load bearing structures- Single room & 2 rooms.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

Preparation of detailed and abstract estimates for the following Civil Engineering works – Buildings – RCC framed structures with flat, sloped RCC roofs with all Building components.

ESTIMATES: Manhole and septic tanks, RCC Culverts.

MEASUREMENT OF EARTHWORK FOR ROADS: Methods for computation of earthwork – cross sections – mid section formula or average end area or mean sectional area, trapezoidal &prismoidal formula with and without cross slopes.

08 hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

SPECIFICATIONS: Definition of specifications, objective of writing specifications, essentials in

specifications, general and detail specifications of common item of works in buildings.

RATE ANALYSIS: Definition and purpose. Working out quantities and rates for the following standard items of works – earth work in different types of soils, cement concrete of different mixes, bricks and stone masonry, flooring, plastering, RCC works, centering and form work for different RCC items, wood and steel works for doors, windows and ventilators. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

CONTRACTS: Types of contract – essentials of contract agreement – legal aspects, penal provisions on breach of contract. Definition of the terms –Tender, earnest money deposit, security deposit, tender forms, documents and types. Acceptance of contract documents. Termination of contract, completion certificate, quality control, right of contractor, refund of deposit. Administrative approval – Technical sanction. Nominal muster roll, measurement books – procedure for recording and checking measurements –preparation of bills. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

Valuation- Definitions of various terms, types of property, depreciation, sinking fund method, Freehold & Leasehold properties, obsolescence, gross income, Outgoings and net incomes, capitalized value and year's purchase. Rental method of valuation and typical problems. **08 hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Estimating & Costing, B. N. Dutta, Chand Publisher
2. Quantity Surveying- P.L. Basin S. Chand, New Delhi.
3. Estimating & Specification - S.C. Rangwala, Charotar publishing house, Anand.

REFERENCES

1. Text book of Estimating & Costing- G.S. Birde, Dhanpath Rai and sons: New Delhi.
2. A text book on Estimating, Costing and Accounts- D.D. Kohliand R.C. Kohli S. Chand, New Delhi.
3. Contracts and Estimates, B. S. Patil, University Press, 2006.

7th Semester B. Tech
PRE STRESSED CONCRETE

Sub Code : 21SCV73
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To learn the principles, materials, methods and systems of prestressing
2. To know the different types of losses and deflection of prestressed members
3. To learn the design of prestressed concrete beams for flexural, shear and tension and to calculate ultimate flexural strength of beam
4. To learn the design of anchorage zones, composite beams, analysis and design of continuous beam
5. To learn the design of water tanks.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Understanding of the behavior of prestressed concrete structures which is an advanced topic of civil engineering.
- CO2:** Able Knowledge of calculation of effect of prestressing on statically determinate structures and statically indeterminate structures.
- CO3:** Design, analysis, detailing and construction of prestressed concrete structural.
- CO4:** Able Develop knowledge of contemporary issues.
- CO5:** Use the techniques, skill, and modern engineering tools necessary for pre-tensioning technology and post-tensioning technology.

MODULE 1

MATERIALS: High strength concrete and steel, Stress-Strain characteristics and properties.

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF PRESTRESSING: Fundamentals, Load balancing concept, Stress concept, center of Thrust. Pre-tensioning and post tensioning systems, tensioning methods and end anchorages. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

ANALYSIS OF SECTIONS FOR FLEXURE: Stresses in concrete due to prestress and loads, stresses in steel due to loads, Cable profiles.

LOSSES OF PRE-STRESS: Various losses encountered in pre-tensioning and post tensioning methods, determination of jacking force. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

DEFLECTIONS: Deflection of a pre-stressed member – Short term and long term deflections, Elastic deflections under transfer loads and due to different cable profiles. Deflection limits as per IS 1343. Effect of creep on deflection, load versus deflection curve, methods of reducing deflection.

08 hours

MODULE 4

LIMIT STATE OF COLLAPSE: Flexure - IS Code recommendations –Ultimate flexural strength of sections. Shear - IS Code recommendations, shear resistance of sections, shear reinforcement. Limit state of serviceability – control of deflections and cracking.

08 hours

MODULE 5

DESIGN OF END BLOCKS: Transmission of prestress in pretensioned members, transmission length, Anchorage stress in post-tensioned members. Bearing stress and bursting tensile force-stresses in end blocks-Methods, IS Code, provision for the design of end block reinforcement.

DESIGN OF BEAMS: Design of pre-tensioned and post-tensioned symmetrical and asymmetrical sections. Permissible stress, design of prestressing force and eccentricity, limiting zone of prestressing force cable profile.

08 hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Pre-stressed Concrete- N. Krishna Raju - Tata Mc Graw Publishers.
2. Pre-stressed Concrete- P. Dayarathnam, Oxford and IBH Publishing Co.
3. Design of pre-stressed concrete structures- T.Y. Lin and Ned H. Burns - John Wiley & Sons, New York.

REFERENCES

1. Fundamental of pre-stressed concrete- N.C. Sinha & S.K. Roy
2. IS: 1343: 1980
3. Pre-stressed Concrete- N. Rajgopalan

7th Semester B. Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 21SCV74
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To Understand Quality Aspects of the water
2. Gain Knowledge about Water Treatment Methods
3. Understands the Criteria for the sewer Design
4. Understands methods of Disposal of effluents
5. Knowledge of Process of Treatment of waste water

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the importance of Quality Aspects of water.

CO2: Able Understands design Criteria of sewer and Sewerage treatment plant.

CO3: Evaluate the degree of treatment and type of treatment for disposal, reuse and recycle.

CO4: Able to manage sewage and industrial effluent issues.

CO5: Able to assess and maintain the IS codal provisions dealing with environmental aspects and treatment of waste water.

MODULE 1

QUALITY OF WATER: Objectives of water quality management. Wholesomeness & palatability, water borne diseases. Water quality parameters – Physical, Chemical and Microbiological. Sampling of water for examination. Water quality analysis (IS 3025 and IS 1622) using analytical and instrumental techniques. Drinking water standards BIS & WHO guidelines. Health significance of Fluoride, Nitrates and heavy metals like Mercury, Cadmium, Arsenic etc and toxic / trace organics.

08 hours

MODULE 2

WATER TREATMENT SEDIMENTATION: Theory, settling tanks, types, design. Coagulant aided sedimentation, jar test, chemical feeding, flash mixing, and Clariflocculator.

FILTRATION: Mechanism – theory of filtration, types of filters, slow sand, rapid sand and pressure filters including construction, operation, cleaning and their design – excluding under drainage system – back washing of filters. Operational problems in filters.

DISINFECTION: Theory of disinfection, types of disinfection, Chlorination, chlorine demand, residual chlorine, use of bleaching powder. UV irradiation treatment – treatment of swimming pool water.

SOFTENING – definition, methods of removal of hardness by lime soda process and zeolite process RO & Membrane technique.

08 hours

MODULE 3

WASTE WATER DISPOSAL & DESIGN OF SEWERS: Necessity for sanitation, methods of domestic waste water disposal, types of sewerage systems and their suitability. Dry weather flow, factors affecting dry weather flow, flow variations and their effects on design of sewerage system; computation of design flow, estimation of storm flow, rational method and empirical formulae of design of storm water drain. Time of concentration.

DESIGN OF SEWERS: Hydraulic formulae for velocity, effects of flow variations on velocity, self-cleansing and non-scouring velocities, Design of hydraulic elements for circular sewers flowing full and flowing partially full (No derivations). **08 hours**

MODULE 4

SEWER MATERIALS AND APPURTENANCES: Sewer materials, shapes of sewers, laying of sewers, joints and testing of sewers, ventilation and cleaning of sewers. Catch basins, manholes, flushing tanks, oil and grease traps, Drainage traps. Basic principles of house drainage. Typical layout plan showing house drainage connections, maintenance of house drainage.

WASTE WATER CHARACTERIZATION: Sampling, significance, techniques and frequency. Physical, Chemical and Biological characteristics, Aerobic and Anaerobic activity, CNS cycles. BOD and COD. Their significance & problems **08 hours**

MODULE 5

DISPOSAL OF EFFLUENTS & TREATMENT OF WASTE WATER:

Disposal of effluents by dilution, self-purification phenomenon. Oxygen sag curve, Zones of purification, Sewage farming, sewage sickness, Effluent Disposal standards for land, surface water & ocean. Flow diagram of municipal waste water treatment plant. Preliminary & Primary treatment: Screening, gritchambers, skimming tanks, primary sedimentation tanks –Design criteria.

SECONDARY TREATMENT: Suspended growth and fixed film bio process. Trickling filter theory and operation, types and designs. Activated sludge process – Principle and flow diagram, Modifications of ASP, F/M ratio. Anaerobic Sludge digestion, Sludge digestion tanks, Low cost waste treatment method. Septic tank, Oxidation Pond and Oxidation ditches. Reuse and recycle of waste water. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Water Supply Engineering – S K Garg, Khanna Publishers
2. Environmental Engineering I – B C Punima and Ashok Jain
3. Manual on Water Supply and Treatment – CPHEEO, Ministry of Urban Development, New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Hammer M.J. (1986), Water and Waste Water Technology – SI Version, 2nd Edition, John Wiley and Sons.
2. Karia G.L. and Christian R.A., 2006), Wastewater Treatment – Concepts and Design Approach, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Metcalf and Eddy (2003), Wastewater Engineering, Treatment and Reuse, 4th Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd.
4. Peavy H.S., Rowe D.R. and Tchobanoglous G. (1986), Environmental Engineering–McGraw Hill Book Co.
5. Raju B.S.N. (1995), Water Supply and Wastewater Engineering, Tata McGraw Hill Pvt. Ltd., NewDelhi.
6. Sincero A.P. and Sincero G.A. (1999), Environmental Engineering – A Design Approach, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
7. Water and Wastewater Engineering, Vol-II:-Fair, Geyer and Okun: John Willey Publishers, New York.

7th Semester B. Tech
DESIGN OF BRIDGES- CORE ELECTIVE -3

Sub Code : 21SCV751
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. Students will be able to understand the analysis and design of concrete Bridges.
2. Students will be able to know the various loads that act on the bridges as per IRC.
3. Students will be able to analyze for the maximum BM and SF at critical section using load distributing theories.
4. Students will be able to design of various components using limit state method with reinforcement details.

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Students will be able to understand the load distribution and IRC standards.

CO2: Student will be familiar with Design the slab and T beam bridges.

CO3: Students will be familiar with Design Box culvert, pipe culvert.

CO4: Manage sewage and industrial effluent issues. Students will be able to use bearings, hinges and expansion joints.

CO5: Students will be able to understand the Design Piers and abutments.

MODULE 1

Introduction: Historical Developments, Site Selection for Bridges, Classification of Bridges Forces on Bridges. Bridge substructures: Abutments, piers and wing walls Balanced Cantilever Bridge: Introduction and proportioning. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

Box Culvert: Different Loading Cases IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled and Class A Loading, working out the worst combination of loading, Moment Distribution, Calculation of BM & SF with Reinforcement. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

Slab Culvert: Different Loading Cases IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled and Class A Loading, working out the worst combination of loading, Moment Distribution, Calculation of BM & SF with Reinforcement. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

T Beam Bridge Slab Design: Proportioning of Components Analysis of interior Slab & Cantilever

Slab Using IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled Class A Loading, Structural Design of Slab, with Reinforcement. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

T Beam Bridge Cross Girder Design: Analysis of Cross Girder for Dead Load & Live Load Using IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled Class A Loading A Loads, Structural Design of Beam with Reinforcement Details. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. “Essentials of Bridge Engineering”- D Johnson Victor, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co New Delhi.
2. “Design of Bridges”- N Krishna Raju, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co New Delhi.
3. “Principles and Practice of Bridge Engineering”- S P BindraDhanpatRai& Sons New Delhi.

REFERENCES

1. Raina V.K., “Concrete Bridge Practice” - Tata McGraw Hill
2. Bakht B & Jaeggar, “Bridge Analysis Simplified” - McGraw Hill
3. Ponnuswamy . S, “Bridge Engineering” - Tata McGraw Hill.
4. Derrick Beckett, “An Introduction to Structural Design of Concrete Bridges”, Surrey University Press.
5. IRC 6 - 1966 “Standard Specifications and Code of Practice for Road Bridges”- Section II Loads and Stresses, The Indian Road Congress New Delhi.
6. IRC 21 - 1966 “Standard Specifications And Code Of Practice For Road Bridges”-Section III Cement Concrete (Plain and reinforced) The Indian Road Congress New Delhi.
7. IS 456 - 2000 “Indian Standard Plain and Reinforced Concrete Code of Practice”- (Fourth Revision) BIS New Delhi.
8. IS 1343 - “Indian Standard Pre stressed Concrete Code of Practice”- BIS New Delhi.

7th Semester B.Tech

DISASTER MANAGEMENT AND MITIGATION

Sub Code : 21SCV752

Hrs / Week : 3

Credits : 3

Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50

Exams Hours : 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To make the student understand various disasters and concepts
2. To make student understand various techniques of Disaster
3. To make student understand the methods of risk reduction
4. To make the student to know regarding the national policy on disaster
5. To make the student to understand disaster management

COURSE OUTCONES:

CO1: Student will understand the concepts of the disasters.

CO2: Students understand the forecasts and the early warning systems

CO3: Students understand the concept of rehabilitation and reconstruction

CO4: Students get acquainted with government policies, acts and various organizational structures associated with an emergency and disaster management

CO5: Student understands the Participation by voluntary agencies and communities.

MODULE 1

Concepts of disaster; Types of disasters - natural and manmade: Cyclone, flood, landslide, land subsidence, fire and earthquake, tsunami, coastal erosion, river erosion, chemical spills, nuclear disasters, mine disasters etc.; Psychological and Social Dimensions in Disasters, Trauma and Stress, Direct and indirect effects of disasters, long term effects of disasters. Introduction to global warming and climate change. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Techniques of monitoring and design against disasters: Forecasting and early warning; Communications & IT Tools, Disaster risk reduction through prevention, Preparedness, Disaster Mitigation, Disaster Response, Disaster Recovery, Rehabilitation and Reconstruction. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Institutional Framework for Disaster Management in India: Importance of public awareness, Preparation and execution of emergency management programme, Scope and responsibilities of National Institute of Disaster Management (NIDM) and National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) in India, Methods and measures to avoid disasters, Management of casualties, Set up of

emergency facilities, Importance of effective communication amongst different agencies in such situations. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Management Issues Related to Disaster: national Policy on disaster management, Legislative responsibilities, Mitigation through capacity building, Disaster Mapping, Disaster Assessment, Pre-disaster risk and vulnerability reduction. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Post Disaster Recovery & Rehabilitation: Participation by voluntary Agencies & Community at various stages of disaster management; disaster related infrastructure development, Use of Internet and software for effective disaster management. Applications of GIS, Remote sensing and GPS in this regard. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Pradeep Sahni, 2004, Disaster Risk Reduction in South Asia, Prentice Hall.
2. Singh B.K., 2008, Handbook of Disaster Management: techniques & Guidelines, Rajat Publication.
3. Ghosh G.K., 2006, Disaster Management, APH Publishing Corporation.
4. Gupta A.K., Niar S.S and Chatterjee S. (2013) Disaster management and Risk Reduction, Role of Environmental Knowledge, Narosa Publishing House, Delhi.

REFERENCES:

1. Murthy D.B.N. (2012) Disaster Management, Deep and Deep Publication PVT. Ltd. New Delhi.
2. Modh S. (2010) Managing Natural Disasters, Mac Millan publishers India LTD.
3. <http://ndma.gov.in/> (Home page of National Disaster Management Authority).
4. <http://www.ndmindia.nic.in/> (National Disaster Management in India, Ministry of Home Affairs).

7thSemester B. Tech

EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT STRUCTURES CORE ELECTIVE -3

Sub Code : 21SCV753
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To provide a coherent development to the students for the courses in sector of earthquake engineering.
2. To present the foundations of many basic engineering concepts related earthquake Engineering.
3. To give an experience in the implementation of engineering concepts which are applied in field of earthquake engineering.
4. To involve the application of scientific and technological principles of planning, analysis, design of buildings according to earthquake design philosophy.

COURSEOUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the principles of engineering seismology, Design and develop analytical skills.
- CO2:** Students will be able to summarize the Seismic evaluation and retrofitting of structures to give an exposure to earthquake engineering.
- CO3:** Students will be able to evaluate seismic forces for various structures as per relevant Indian standards
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand the design and ductile detailing of structures for seismic resistance as per Indian standards.
- CO5:** Students will able to understand apply concepts of repair and rehabilitation of earthquake affected structures.

MODULE 1

Introduction to engineering seismology, Geological and tectonic features of India, Origin and propagation of seismic waves, characteristics of earthquake and its quantification - Magnitude and Intensity scales, seismic instruments. Earthquake Hazards in India, Earthquake Risk Evaluation and Mitigation. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

Structural behavior under gravity and seismic loads, Lateral load resisting structural systems, Requirements of efficient earthquake resistant structural system, damping devises, base isolation systems. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

The Response history and strong motion characteristics. Response Spectrum - elastic and inelastic response spectra, tripartite (D-V-A) response spectrum, use of response spectrum in earthquake resistant design. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

Design of Computation of seismic forces in multistoried buildings - using procedures (Equivalent lateral force and dynamic analysis) as per IS-1893. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

Design of Reinforced concrete buildings for earthquake resistance-Load combinations, Ductility and energy absorption in buildings. Confinement of concrete for ductility, design of columns and beams for ductility, ductile detailing provisions as per IS-1893. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Dynamics of Structures - Theory and Application to Earthquake Engineering- 2nd ed. - Anil K. Chopra, Pearson Education.
2. Earthquake Resistant Design of Building Structures, Vinod Hosur, WILEY (India)
3. Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures, Duggal, Oxford University Press.

REFERENCES

1. IS - 1893 (Part I): 2002, IS - 13920: 1993, IS - 4326: 1993, IS-13828: 1993
2. Design of Earthquake Resistant Buildings, Minoru Wakabayashi, McGraw Hill Pub.
3. Seismic Design of Reinforced Concrete and Masonry Buildings, T Paulay and M J N Priestley, John Wiley and Sons.

**7th Semester B.Tech
PAVEMENT DESIGN**

Sub Code : 21SCV754
Hrs / Week : 3
Credits : 3
Mode of Delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exams Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study about the types and components of pavements
2. To learn about the stresses in flexible pavements and equivalent single wheel load
3. To study the design of flexible pavements
4. To learn about the stresses in rigid pavements, design of dowel and tie bars
5. To study the failures, maintenance and evaluation of life of flexible and rigid pavements.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Identify the pavement components and compare highway and airport pavements
CO2: Calculate stresses and ESWL in flexible pavements
CO3: Design the flexible pavement using empirical and semi empirical methods
CO4: Analyze the warping, friction, wheel load stress, calculate the combined stress, design dowel and tie bars in rigid pavements
CO5: Analyze and Evaluate different types of failures, and suggest remedial measures for the maintenance of flexible and rigid pavement.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Desirable characteristics of pavement, Type's and components, Difference between Highway pavement and Air field pavement, Design strategies of variables, Functions of Sub-grade, Sub base, Base course, Surface course, Comparison between Rigid and Flexible pavement.

FUNDAMENTALS OF DESIGN OF PAVEMENTS: Design life – Traffic factors – climatic factors – Road geometry – Sub grade strength and drainage, Stresses and deflections, Boussinesq's theory – principle, Assumptions – Limitations and problems on above - Burmister theory – Two layered analysis – Assumptions – problems on above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 2

DESIGN FACTORS: Design wheel load – contact pressure – ESWL concept – Determination of ESWL by graphical method - Equivalent deflection criteria – Stress criteria – EWL concept.

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT DESIGN: McLeod Method – Kansas method – Tri-axial method - CBR method – IRC Method (old) - CSA Method using IRC 37-2001. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 3

STRESSES IN RIGID PAVEMENT: Principle – Factors - Wheel load and its repetition – Properties of sub grade - External conditions – Joints – Reinforcement – Analysis of stresses - Assumptions – Westergaard’s Analysis – Modified Westergaard’s equations – Critical stresses - Wheel load stresses, Warping stress – Frictional stress – combined stresses (using chart / equations) - problems on above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF RIGID PAVEMENT: Design of C.C. Pavement by IRC: 58 –2002 for dual and Tandem axle load – Reinforcement in slabs – Requirements of joints – Types of joints – Expansion joint – contraction joint– warping joint – construction joint – longitudinal joint, Design of joints, Design of Dowel bars, Design of Tie bars – problems on the above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 5

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE AND EVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in flexible pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurement by using different techniques - Structural Evaluation by Benkelman Beam Deflection Method, Falling weight deflectometer, GPR Method.

RIGID PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE AND EVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in rigid pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurements.

Design factors for Runway Pavements - Design methods for Airfield pavements. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Highway Engineering - Khanna & Justo
2. Principles & Practices of Highway Engineering- L R Kadiyalli & N B. Lal
3. Pavement Analysis & Design - Yang H. Huang- II edition.
4. IRC 37 and IRC 58 codes

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Principles of Pavement Design- Yoder and Witzack - 2nd edition, John Wileys and Sons
2. Principles of Pavement Design- Subha Rao
3. IRC 37 Code Book
4. IRC 58 Code Book

7th Semester B. Tech

ADVANCED CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY CORE ELECTIVE -3

Sub Code : 21SCV755
Hrs/ Week : 3T
Credits : 3
Mode of delivery: RM

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To understand on cement chemistry and influence of other cementitious materials to the progress of hydration reaction.
2. To know chemical and physical interaction of aggregates and admixtures with the hydrated cement paste and their effects on the performance of fresh and hardened concrete.
3. To know concrete durability problems.
4. Expected physical and chemical changes occurring on the concrete microstructure during the progress of durability problems and precautions to be taken.
5. Manufacture of special concretes and their properties.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Discuss the concrete ingredients and its influence at gaining strength.

CO2: Design of concrete mix and grade as per IS codes.

CO3: Summarize the concepts of conventional concrete and its differences with other concretes like no fines, light weight etc.

CO4: Describe the application and use of fiber reinforced concrete.

CO5: Design and develop the self-compacting and high performance concrete.

MODULE 1

Importance of Bogue's compounds, Structure of a Hydrated Cement Paste, Volume of hydrated product, porosity of paste and concrete, transition Zone, Elastic Modulus, factors affecting strength and elasticity of concrete, Rheology of concrete in terms of Bingham's parameter.

CHEMICAL ADMIXTURES - Mechanism of chemical admixture, Plasticizers and super Plasticizers and their effect on concrete property in fresh and hardened state, retarder, accelerator, Air-entraining admixtures, new generation super plasticiser. **08 hours**

MODULE 2

MINERAL ADMIXTURE - Fly ash, Silica fume, GCBS, and their effect on concrete property in fresh state and hardened state.

MIX DESIGN - Factors affecting mix design, design of concrete mix by BIS method using IS10262 and current American (ACI)/ British (BS) methods. Provisions in revised IS10262-2004. **08 hours**

MODULE 3

DURABILITY OF CONCRETE - Introduction, Permeability of concrete, chemical attack, acid attack, efflorescence, Corrosion in concrete. Thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, specific heat. Alkali Aggregate Reaction, IS456-2000 requirement for durability. **08 hours**

MODULE 4

RMC concrete - manufacture, transporting, placing, precautions, Methods of concreting- Pumping, under water concreting, shotcrete, High volume fly ash concrete, Self-compacting concrete concept and tests.

Fiber reinforced concrete - Fibers types and properties, Ferro cement - materials, techniques of manufacture, properties and application. **08 hours**

MODULE 5

Light weight concrete-materials properties and types. Typical light weight concrete mix High density concrete and high performance concrete-materials, properties and applications.

Test on Hardened concrete- Compression, tension and flexure tests. NDT tests concepts-Rebound hammer, pulse velocity methods. **08 hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Properties of Concrete- Neville, A.M. - ELBS Edition, Longman Ltd., London
2. Concrete Technology- M.S. Shetty
3. Concrete Technology- A.R. Santhakumar, Oxford University Press.
4. Concrete- P.K. Mehta, P J M Monteiro, Prentice Hall, New Jersey (Special Student Edition by Indian Concrete Institute Chennai)
5. ACI Code for Mix Design and IS 10262-2004.
6. Concrete Mix Design- N. Krishna Raju, Sehgal Publishers.

REFERENCES

1. Concrete Manual- Gambhir M.L., Dhanpat Rai & Sons, New Delhi.
2. Advanced Concrete Technology Processes- John Newman, Ban Seng Choo, London.
3. Advanced Concrete Technology Constituent materials- John Newman, Ban Seng Choo, London.
4. Non-Destructive Test and Evaluation of Materials- J. Prasad, C GK Nair,-McGraw Hill.

7th Semester B.Tech

DETAILING & DRAWING OF STEEL STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 21SCVL76

IA Marks : 25

Hrs / Week : 3

Exams Hours : 2

Credits : 1

Exam Marks : 25

Mode of Delivery: RM

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To analyse and design the steel members (beams and columns) and connections (bolted and welded).
2. To understand the concept of buckling, shear, bending of members subjected to combined forces acting on different members
3. To understand the design of structural steel components (members and connections in two – dimensional truss and frame structures).
4. Ability to perform analysis and design of gantry girder and design of steel structural systems as per the latest IS code.
5. Assess the effective use of the latest industry standard formulas, tables, design aids in the design of steel members.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the loads and loads combination acting on structural members as per IS code.

CO2: Design tension and compression members using simple and built-up sections.

CO3: Design simple bolted and welded connections for tension and compression members and beams.

CO4: Able to calculate forces on the various members of the truss and design them.

CO5: Able to design the gantry girder by considering optimum and economical section.

PART - A

(Drawings to be prepared for the given structural details)

MODULE 1

CONNECTIONS:

Bolted and Welded connections, Beam to Beam connection, Beam to Column connection, Seated connection, Stiffened connection and Un-stiffened connection. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

COLUMNS:

Splices between steel structures, Column to Column of same dimensions / sections and Splicing between Column to Column of different sections.

Connections by using Single Lacing, Double Lacing and Battens.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

COLUMN BASES:

Slab Base foundation details for normal loading condition and Gusseted Base foundation details for heavy loading and lateral forces. **10 Hours**

PART - B

(Design and Drawing of following)

MODULE 4

Design of Roof Truss by using bolted connection, including Bottom chord, Top chord and Vertical members, Forces acting in the members to be given. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Design of electrically operated Gantry Girder, by using Welded connection, combination of standard sections, Channel, Cover Plates, I section. **10 Hours**

Note: Study of this course should be based on IS: 800-2007

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Part A	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
2	Assignment / Drawings on Steel Structures	Regular Mode of Assessment	25
3	Open Book Test on Design of Roof Truss / Gantry Girder (Part B)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **THREE** questions, Choosing **ONE** full question from each module.

(10 Mark x 3 Questions = 30 Marks)

PART B:

ONE question to be set from each module. Students have to answer any **ONE** full question

(20 Mark x 1 Question = 20 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Structural Design & Drawing – N. Krishna Raju, Universities Press, India
2. Design of Steel Structures, N. Subramanian, Oxford, 2008
3. Design of Steel Structures - Negi - Tata McGraw Hill Publishers
4. Limit State Design of Steel Structures, Duggal. TATA Megra Hill 2010

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Design of Steel Structures – Raghupati
2. Bureau of Indian Standards, IS800-2007, IS875-1987
3. Steel Table – Birla Publications, New Delhi.

7th Semester B. Tech

ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING LABORATORY

Sub Code : 21SCVL77
Hrs/ Week : 2L
Credits : 1
Mode of delivery: BM

IA Marks : 25
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 25
Total Hours : 30

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

1. To quantify the water and wastewater pollutant
2. To measure the concentration of air pollutants
3. To analyze the characteristics of water, wastewater and ambient air
4. To study the growth of microorganism and its quantification
5. To analyze optimum dosage of coagulant

COURSEOUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Quantify the pollutant concentration in water, wastewater and ambient air.
CO2: Recommend the degree of treatment required for the water and wastewater.
CO3: Analyze the survival conditions for the microorganism and its growth rate.
CO4: Determine physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water and wastewater.
CO5: Determine optimum dosage of coagulant.

EXPERIMENTS - 30 hours

1. Determination of Solids in Sewage: Total Solids, Suspended Solids, Dissolved Solids, Volatile Solids, Fixed Solids, Settleable Solids.
2. Electrical conductivity. Determination of Chlorides and Sulphates.
3. Determination of Alkalinity, Acidity and pH.
4. Determination of Calcium, Magnesium and Total Hardness.
5. Determination of Dissolved Oxygen. Determination of BOD.
6. Determination of COD.
7. Determination of percentage of available chlorine in bleaching powder, Residual Chlorine and Chlorine Demand.
8. Jar Test for Optimum Dosage of Alum, Turbidity determination by Nephelometer.
9. Determination of Iron, Phenanthroline method.
10. Determination of Fluorides SPANDS Method.
11. Determination Nitrates by spectrophotometer.
12. Determination of sodium and potassium by flame photometer.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS

1. Manual of Water and Wastewater Analysis – NEERI Publication.
2. Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Waste water(1995), American Publication – Association, Water Pollution Control Federation, American Water Works Association, Washington DC.

REFERENCES

1. IS Standards: 2490-1974, 3360-1974, 3307-1974.
2. Chemistry for Environment Engineering. Sawyer and McCarthy.

**7TH Semester B.Tech
INTERNSHIP - 2**

Sub Code : 21SCV78
Hrs/ Week : 6
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: ---
Total Marks : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their internship area / topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

CO1: Present the work done in his/her internship on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the presentation with sound technical knowledge and communication skills.

Instructions:

Following are the guidelines to be followed for the Internship Programme:

1. The Internship Programme duration is of Four weeks.
2. The internship can be carried out in any industry / R and D Organization / Research Institute / Educational institute of repute.
3. The institutions may also suggest the students to enroll for the Internshala platform for free internships as there is MoU with the AICTE for the beneficial of the affiliated Institutions (<https://internshala.com/>)
4. The Examination of Internship will be carried out in line with the University Project Viva-Voce examination.
5. The Department/college shall nominate staff member/s to facilitate, guide and supervise students under internship.
6. The students shall report the progress of the internship to the guide in regular intervals and seek his/her advice.
7. After the completion of Internship, students shall submit a report with completion and attendance certificates to the Head of the Department with the approval of both internal and external guides.

8. There will be 50 marks for CIE (Seminar: 20, Internship report: 20) and 10 marks for Viva - Voce. The minimum requirement of CIE marks shall be 50% of the maximum marks.
9. The internal guide shall award the marks for seminar and internship report after evaluation. He/she will also be the internal examiner for Viva-Voce.
10. The external guide from the industry shall be an examiner for the viva voce on Internship. Viva-Voce on internship shall be conducted at the college and the date of Viva-Voce shall be fixed in consultation with the external Guide. The Examiners shall jointly award the Viva- Voce marks.
11. In case the external Guide expresses his inability to conduct viva voce, the HoD shall appoint a senior faculty of the Department to conduct viva-voce along with the internal guide. The same shall be informed in writing to the concerned Chairperson, Board of Examiners (BOE).
12. The students are permitted to carry out the internship anywhere in India or abroad. The University will not provide any kind of financial assistance to any student for carrying out the Internship.

Scheme of Examination:

Total: 50 marks

7TH Semester B.Tech

EMPLOYABILITY SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME - IPR AND PATENT FILING

Sub Code : 21SQA79

IA Marks : 50

Hrs/ Week : 6

Exam Hours : ---

Credits : 2

Exam Marks: ---

Total Marks : 50

Objectives:

1. To introduce fundamental aspects of Intellectual property Rights to students who are going to play a major role in development and management of innovative projects in industries.
2. To disseminate knowledge on patents, patent regime in India and abroad and registration aspects
3. To disseminate knowledge on copyrights and its related rights and registration aspects
4. To disseminate knowledge on trademarks and registration aspects
5. To disseminate knowledge on Design, Geographical Indication (GI), Plant Variety and Layout Design Protection and their registration aspects
6. To aware about current trends in IPR and Govt. steps in fostering IPR

Course Outcomes

CO1: The students once they complete their academic projects, shall get an adequate knowledge on patent and copyright for their innovative research works

CO2: During their research career, information in patent documents provide useful insight on novelty of their idea from state-of-the art search. This provide further way for developing their idea or innovations

CO3: Pave the way for the students to catch up Intellectual Property(IP) as an career option

- a. R&D IP Counsel
- b. Government Jobs – Patent Examiner
- c. Private Jobs
- d. Patent agent and Trademark agent
- e. Entrepreneur

Module 1 - Overview of Intellectual Property

Introduction and the need for intellectual property right (IPR) - Kinds of Intellectual Property Rights: Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Design, Geographical Indication, Plant Varieties and Layout Design – Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge – Trade Secret - IPR in India : Genesis and development – IPR in abroad - Major International Instruments concerning Intellectual Property Rights: Paris Convention 1883, the Berne Convention 1886, the Universal

Copyright Convention 1952, the WIPO Convention 1967, the Patent Co-operation Treaty 1970, the TRIPS Agreement 1994. **6 hours**

Module 2 – Patents

Patents - Elements of Patentability: Novelty, Non Obviousness (Inventive Steps), Industrial Application - Non - Patentable Subject Matter - Registration Procedure, Rights and Duties of Patentee, Assignment and license, Restoration of lapsed Patents, Surrender and Revocation of Patents, Infringement, Remedies & Penalties – Patent office and Appellate Board. **6 Hours**

Module 3 – Copyrights

Nature of Copyright - Subject matter of copyright: original literary, dramatic, musical, artistic works; cinematograph films and sound recordings - Registration Procedure, Term of protection, Ownership of copyright, Assignment and license of copyright - Infringement, Remedies & Penalties – Related Rights - Distinction between related rights and copyrights. **6 Hours**

Module 4 - Trademarks and Design

Concept of Trademarks - Different kinds of marks (brand names, logos, signatures, symbols, well known marks, certification marks and service marks) - Non Registrable Trademarks - Registration of Trademarks - Rights of holder and assignment and licensing of marks - Infringement, Remedies & Penalties - Trademarks registry and appellate board.

Design

Design: meaning and concept of novel and original - Procedure for registration, effect of registration and term of protection. **6 Hours**

Module 5 - Patent Filing (Hands on Training)

Purposes and techniques of Patent searching, Art of Drafting, Anatomy of Patent applications. Overall procedure. **6 Hours**

References:

Text Book:

1. Nithyananda, K V. (2019). *Intellectual Property Rights: Protection and Management*. India, IN: Cengage Learning India Private Limited.
2. Neeraj, P., & Khusdeep, D. (2014). *Intellectual Property Rights*. India, IN: PHI learning Private Limited.

Reference book:

1. Ahuja, V K. (2017). *Law relating to Intellectual Property Rights*. India, IN: Lexis Nexis.

E-resources:

1. Subramanian, N., & Sundararaman, M. (2018). *Intellectual Property Rights – An Overview*. Retrieved from <http://www.bdu.ac.in/cells/ipr/docs/ipr-eng-ebook.pdf>

2. World Intellectual Property Organisation. (2004). *WIPO Intellectual property Handbook*. Retrieved from https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/intproperty/489/wipo_pub_489.pdf

Reference Journal:

1. Journal of Intellectual Property Rights (JIPR): NISCAIR

Useful Websites:

1. Cell for IPR Promotion and Management (<http://cipam.gov.in/>)
2. World Intellectual Property Organisation (<https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>)
3. Office of the Controller General of Patents, Designs & Trademarks (<http://www.ipindia.nic.in/>)

**7TH Semester B.Tech
MINI PROJECT**

Sub Code : 21SCV79

Hrs / Week : 3

Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 3

Exam Marks : 50

Total Marks : 100

Course Objectives:

At the end of the course, the student will be able to:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

Instructions/Guidelines:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work.

Students should select a problem which addresses some basic home, office or other real life applications. Students have to collect an International Journal paper on the topics of their interest, prepare a write up and present with suitable demonstration by software or experimental work. Evaluation will be based on relevant topic student has studied, communication skill and reporting/documenting procedure.

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Total: 100 Marks

**7TH Semester B.Tech
SOCIAL INTERNSHIP**

Sub Code : 21SSI01
Hrs/ Week : 6
Credits : ---

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: ---
Total Marks : 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their internship area / topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

- CO1: Expose to the society and its issues / problems and push to build value structures for those who are less fortunate.
- CO2: Take a close and personal look at social issues in which privilege, inequality, marginalization, and powerlessness lead to structural disparities.
- CO3: Present the work done in his/her Social Internship on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.
- CO4: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- CO5: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

Instructions:

Social Internship – a fast growing field offers flexibility and portability, a chance to solve problems and make the world a better place to live. Students can undertake Social Internship in the areas of social justice, women empowerment, rural development, rural water supply and sanitation, solid waste management, traffic regulations and safety, gender inequality, rural education, sustainable development, pollution control, etc which will benefit the large section of people in the society.

Students can do the Social Internship either by working with NGOs or with Companies in the Corporate Social Responsibility sector or with Govt / Semi Govt / Private Organisations and Departments.

Social Internships will help the students to expose to the society and its issues / problems and push them to build value structures for those who are less fortunate. Social Internship will also help the students to take a close and personal look at social issues in which privilege, inequality, marginalization, and powerlessness lead to structural disparities.

Following are the guidelines to be followed for the Internship Programme:

1. The Social Internship Programme is an ongoing activity from first year till the final year.
2. The final report of Social Internship should be submitted at the end of 7th semester.
3. Each student should be allotted a Guide in the Dept of Civil Engineering at the beginning of 3rd semester and the same Guide will monitor and document the progress of Social Internship till the end of 7th semester.
4. The Social Internship can be carried out in any NGO / Research Institute / Govt or Semi Govt or Private Organisation or Department.
5. The Examination of Social Internship will be carried out in line with the University Project Viva-Voce examination.
6. The Department / College shall nominate staff member/s to facilitate, guide and supervise students under social internship.
7. The students shall report the progress of the Social Internship to the guide in regular intervals at the end of academic year and seek his/her advice.
8. After the completion of Social Internship, students shall submit a report with completion and attendance certificates to the Head of the Department with the approval of both internal and external guides.
9. There will be 100 marks for CIE (Work done: 50, Seminar: 20, Internship report: 20) and 10 marks for Viva - Voce. The minimum requirement of CIE marks shall be 50% of the maximum marks.
10. At the end of 7th semester, The internal guide shall award the marks for seminar and internship report after evaluation. He/she will also be the internal examiner for Viva-Voce.
11. The external guide (if any) from the NGO / Research Institute / Govt or Semi Govt or Private Organisation or Department shall be an Examiner for the Viva Voce of Social Internship. Viva-Voce on internship shall be conducted at the college and the date of Viva-Voce shall be fixed in consultation with the External Guide. The Examiners shall jointly award the Viva- Voce marks.
12. In case the External Guide expresses his/her inability to conduct viva voce, the HoD shall appoint a senior faculty from the Department to conduct viva-voce along with the internal guide. The same shall be informed in writing to the concerned Chairperson, Board of Examiners (BOE).
13. The students are permitted to carry out the Social Internship anywhere in India or abroad. The University will not provide any kind of financial assistance to any student for carrying out the Internship.

Scheme of Examination:

Total: 100 marks

8th Semester B.Tech
SEMINAR

Sub Code : 21SCV81
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: ---
Total Marks : 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected Seminar topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the seminar with sound technical knowledge and communication skills.

Instructions:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Seminar. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected Seminar, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the Seminar work

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Total: 100 marks

8th Semester B. Tech
MOOC 3 (RESEARCH METHODOLOGY)

Subject Code	21SCVS03	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-	Total Marks	50
Credits	1		

Course Objectives:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Improve learnability

CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study

CO3: Develop the skill

CO4: Industry ready

CO5: Have more confidence level

About the Course:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

Assessment Method for MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The Students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.
- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weightage	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs & Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

VIII Semester B.Tech
PROJECT WITH APPLIED PATENT

Sub Code :	21SCV82	IA Marks :	100
Hrs/ Week :	26	Exam Hours :	---
Credits :	12	Exam Marks:	100
		Total Marks :	200

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to:

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected Project orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

Instructions:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey / visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work

1. Two reviews will be conducted (excluding the external review). Apart from this the guides have to review the project and the project report as per the specified guidelines.
2. The students have to submit the abstract (as per the given format) and based on willingness of the guide the students are permitted for Project work.
3. The assessments will be done in the scaling of 1-5 for each component of the project done through rubrics.

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Distribution of the marks is as follows:

Part 1 (Internal Evaluation): 100 marks

Part 2 (External Evaluation): 100 marks

Total: 200 marks

Marks distribution (Internal Evaluation): 100 marks

- Continuous Assessment: 40 marks (Regularity, Working as a Team)
- Guide's Evaluation: 30 marks (Technical Knowledge, Awareness)
- Presentation with PPT: 20 marks
- Journal Publication: 10 marks

Marks distribution (External Evaluation): 100 marks

This includes the following:

- Title and Concept of the Project – 10 marks
- Scope, Problem Definition and Objective of the Project – 10 marks
- Literature Review – 10 marks
- Methodology and Work details – 30 marks
- Conclusion and Discussion – 10 marks
- Journal Publication – 10 marks
- Overall presentation – 20 marks